

H2020-FNR-2020-2 LC-FNR-13-2020

CREATING ADDED-VALUE CHEMICALS FROM BIO-INDUSTRIAL CO₂
EMISSIONS USING INTEGRATED CATALYTIC TECHNOLOGIES

D7.8 – Dissemination and Communication Plan (Update from M1 to M54)

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*This document corresponds to D7.8 and describes the Communication and Dissemination Plan (contract no. 101000580) carried out by the CATCO2NVERS project during the project lifetime, whose main objective was to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) were consequently disseminated to the appropriate target communities. **The updates are included in the Section 14 Actions from M31-M54***

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1 Executive summary

This document contains a detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan that outlines the project's audiences and communication channels for dissemination. It also answers the questions WHO? WHAT? WHEN? HOW? and provides an integrated, accurate, and efficient dissemination strategy. In addition, it highlights potential audiences, roles and responsibilities, and methods of communication to be used for the CATCO2NVERS tool promotion.

Task 7.1 aims at proactively promoting the CATCO2NVERS project and its results by providing targeted information to various audiences. The promotion activities will be part of the dissemination and communication plan, and this document presents the first step in achieving the partial objective.

2 Acronyms and abbreviations

BIOR	Bio-refineries
CD	Catalyst developers
DCP	Dissemination and communication plan
DoA	Description of Activities
FDME	Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester
FME	Furfural Methyl Ester
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Public
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key exploitable result
NADH	Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide
RPMCA	Regulators, Policy Makers & Community Associations
SC	Scientific Community
SIE	Sustainable Innovations Europe
TD	Technology developers
WP	Work package

3 Introduction

This document describes the Communication and Dissemination Plan to be adopted by the CATCO2NVERS project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to the appropriate target communities.

It, first of all, presents the objectives of the communication and dissemination plan, the main target audiences to follow with the tools and channels. Within these tools and

channels, different means and platforms, such as the website, the social media channels, printed materials, newsletters, press releases, scientific journals, and trade media are explored. In addition, it is also commented the participation in conferences, workshops, and events. The stakeholders' engagement is also explored, to then proceed to evaluate which indicators and targets are set to evaluate the communication efforts.

The communication and dissemination will involve different levels (European level, international level, regional level, etc.) and it will work both externally and internally. These realms are also considered in the plan below.

A timeline with the main three communication phases is presented, to finish with an overview of the actions carried out from M1 to M6.

3.1 Context of WP7

The main objective of this WP is to maximise the impact of the project results during its lifetime and after the project's end. More in detail, the specific objectives are:

- To disseminate the project results among relevant industrial and academic stakeholders.
- To raise awareness among the public about the potential of using CO₂ utilisation technologies coupled to bio-based industries.
- To map and evaluate the market size of CATCO₂NVERS technologies and products within the EU bio-economy.
- To design novel and effective business models to enhance economic profitability of bio-based industries while reducing CO₂ emissions.
- To ensure the exploitation of the project's KER through adequate exploitation plans.

3.2 Objectives of T7.1

The DoA contemplates that a detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan should be produced at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2. and in collaboration with all the consortium; this plan will outline the project's audiences, and communication channels for dissemination. It will provide an integrated, accurate, and efficient dissemination strategy, highlight the potential audiences, roles and responsibilities, and methods of communication to be used. The first list of stakeholders and end-users will be prepared at month 6, to be updated during the project lifetime to include all relevant actors in consultations devoted to better explore the local context and adapt the technologies. The

involvement of stakeholders from the beginning of the project will be crucial to raise awareness about related problems and to enhance the community's acceptance of the proposed efficient exploitation strategies.

4 Objectives of the DCP

The main objective of the CATCO₂NVERS dissemination strategy is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to appropriate target communities. It is anticipated that contributors to CATCO₂NVERS development, evaluation, market uptake, and exploitation are identified and motivated to proactively participate.

A multistep and multichannel approach will be used in the CATCO₂NVERS dissemination strategy in order to reach and engage different stakeholders and target groups with adjusted information for needs and interests. Awareness will be raised to all possible project beneficiaries.

The key specific objectives to achieve the CATCO₂NVERS goals are:

- To disseminate the project results among relevant industrial and academic stakeholders.
- To raise awareness among the public about the potential of using CO₂ utilisation technologies coupled to bio-based industries.
- To build a strong network of stakeholders interested in the project results
- To ensure effective knowledge transfer of CATCO₂NVERS outcomes,

5 Target audiences

CATCO₂NVERS has preliminarily identified a significant list of stakeholders to which the dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed

Table 5.1: Target groups & contents

TARGET GROUP / STAKEHOLDER	TARGETED RESULTS/ CONTENT
Bio-refineries (BIOR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of their emissions & integration of CO₂ in their processes • Synergies between industry sectors • Modelling of decentralized pre-treatment, new processes • Additional yields through carbon conversion technology integration.

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CATCO₂NVERS

Catalyst developers (CD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of new bi-functional heterogeneous catalysts based on organic/inorganic supports • Development of novel immobilized biocatalysts
Technology developers (TD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel route to lactic acid from CO₂ and bioethanol feedstocks • CO₂ conversion to FDME from Furfural - two-step one-pot process • Models for flexible facilities
Regulators, Policy Makers & Community Associations (RPMCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New resources available through the integration of carbon conversion technology in the bio-based industries and its application potential • Potential of carbon conversion technology and advancements for the circular bioeconomy • Need for further scientific research
Scientific Community (SC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results on novel system for production Lactic acid from CO₂ and ethanol • Results on novel NADH regeneration methods • Logistics modelling of bio-based streams in decentralized system, different feedstocks & circularity assessment of bio-CO₂ based products • Synthesis and characterization of new bi-functional heterogeneous catalysts based on porous organic polymers • Synthesis and oxidative esterification of furfural to obtain furfural methyl ester (FME) in soft conditions • Carboxylation of FME with CO₂ to obtain FDME in soft conditions • Furfural to FDME using CO₂ by a two-steps one-pot process
General Public (GP).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the development of a new technology that allows the use of CO₂ to obtain a precursor of bioplastics • New resources without land-use change or food/feed controversy, CO₂ as feedstock, connection to climate change, • Circular economy concept

Several key stakeholders have been already detected by consortium partners, such as Turkish Cosmetics Manufacturers and Researchers Association (Küad), Turkish Quality Association (Kalder), Istanbul Chamber of Industry - European Enterprise Network, Sarten Packaging, Iff (International Flavors & Fragrances Inc), Parkim Group, Sfa Arge, Antimikrop Lab, Plastic Move; and others.

Trade media have already been identified as well: Technology Review, Popular Mechanics, Technology Review, Engineering & Technology, RQ Magazine, Ingenieur, Horizon Magazine, Innovators Magazine, Econoticas, RETEMA, Industria Ambiente and others.

Likewise, similar European projects have been identified to search for synergies such as CO2SMOS, CO2PERATE, eCOCO2 or BIOCON-CO2.

6 Tools and channels

Different tools and channels will be used to disseminate and communicate the activities carried out by CATCO2NVERS and its results. Each tool and channel will be used appropriately to address different target groups at different stages of the proposal implementation, thereby increasing the efficiency of the DCP. The relationship between the tools and channels, the target groups, and the expected results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.1: Channels / Tools / Target groups/ Expected impacts

Channels	Tools	Target Groups	Expected Results	Impact and
Printed Materials	Brochure	Industry, Academia, Manufacturers, End consumers, Associations, Environmental Organisations, Standardisation bodies and policy makers	Inform about the project scope, objectives, impacts, methodology and results.	
	Leaflet			
Online	CATCO2NVERS project website	Scientific community, industry, technology developers, G.Public	(1) Inform about the project scope, objectives, impacts, methodology and results. (2) Keep the audience updated with regular news. (3) Share the public deliverables. (4) Raise awareness on the project technologies.	
	Social Media (Twitter & LinkedIn)			
	Videos			
	Newsletters			
	Press Releases	Media groups and journalists/ General public	Inform about the project scope, objectives, impacts, methodology and results.	

			Raise awareness among on the economic and environmental impacts of the project.
Publications	Scientific Publications	Industry, Academia, Manufacturers, End consumers, Associations, Environmental Organisations	To raise awareness on the economic and environmental impacts of the project. To persuade on the benefits resulting from an uptake of CATCO2NVERS innovations.
Events (Organized)	Workshop Webinars		
Events (Attended)	Workshops	Standardisation bodies & policy makers	To communicate the results obtained.
	Conferences	Industry, Academia, Manufacturers, End consumers, Associations, Environmental Organisations	To share the capacities acquired and encourage replication and exploitation.
	Tradeshows		

Several dissemination tools and channels will be used, including a project website, articles targeted at both a lay and a technical audience, press releases, e-newsletters, scientific papers and leaflets, social media presence, and participation in workshops/conferences.

Any dissemination activities and publications in the project, including the project website, will specify that the project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, as well as displaying the European emblem. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem will be given appropriate prominence. All publications will reference the grant agreement number.

The communication activities within the project are both periodic (management group meetings, newsletters, project group meetings, and reporting to the commission) and online (project restricted area on the website).

Communication activities to stakeholders outside the project group are based on the dissemination plan presented in section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement. The journal articles are primarily intended to communicate the recent findings to the scientific and academic communities. However, the project will also publish in trade journals and magazines important to the industry to disseminate new relevant solutions to other possible end-users. Project presentations at technical conferences are intended to reach the same audience.

6.1 Project identity

A recognisable project identity was developed to build a visual brand and ultimately offer a package of templates that will facilitate the building of notoriety progressively through the project. This includes creating a project logo and an accompanying style guide. These will be consistently used for the project website and all other communication templates, such as PowerPoint, Word, posters, and EC Reports : <https://catco2nvers.eu/documents/>

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 6.1: Brand guidelines

Brand Guidelines

Color palette

#F0F0F0	#333333	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000
#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000
#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000
#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000	#000000

Text/background/icon

#000000
#000000
#000000
#000000

Background/graphic elements

Font setting print & desktop presentation

Title 1 Bold 24pt
Century Gothic #8dc640 Abcdefghi

Subtitle 1 Regular 16pt
Century Gothic #09a9fd Abcdefghi

Title 3 Bold 12pt
Century Gothic #013131 Abcdefghi

Text 1 Regular 11pt
Century Gothic #013131 Abcdefghi

Figures Regular Italic 11pt
Century Gothic #898989 Abcdefghi

Font setting web (Google font)

Montserrat #8dc640 Abcdefghi

Montserrat #09a9fd Abcdefghi

Montserrat #013131 Abcdefghi

Montserrat #013131 Abcdefghi

Montserrat #898989 Abcdefghi

Iconography style

Photography style

Logo variations

Logo

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6.2 Project website

CATCO2NVERS has been given an up-to-date and user-friendly project website (<https://catco2nvers.eu/>) It will be the primary source of information for external parties, providing updates on project activities and achievements to all target audiences. The website aims to inform the scientific community and associated industries about project developments, but also to present the project's achievements and novel pilot lines to the public.

All partners will contribute to the website by providing relevant project information in accessible language (laymen's terms). All communication efforts by project partners and social media will always be redirected to the CATCO2NVERS website. Traffic to the website will be increased by creating mutual links between the partners' websites and other relevant websites.

The project website contains:

- Latest news about the project progress and results
- Details about the project partners
- Informative materials (newsletter, infographics, articles)
- Contact information
- Social media links
- At least two videos (embedded from Youtube). The first one will explain the main objectives and scope of the project. The last one will serve as training material for stakeholders and will be produced by the end of the project.
- Privacy policy, cookies policy, and legal terms to comply with general data protection regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) on the protection of natural persons about the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

The project website is set up by SIE and will be managed, maintained, and hosted for the duration of the project and a further 2 years after the completion of the project. Statistical data will be collected about the website visitors that subsequently will be analysed by Google Analytics software and included in the project reports. The website will be responsive to work on a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as smartphones.

6.3 Content management system

For internal dissemination purposes, consortium partners will have access to a password-protected site (SharePoint established by the coordination, FUNDITEC) which will contain the proposal, consortium agreement, grant agreement, budget, deliverables, periodic reports, meeting, and workshop reports, and other relevant documents. Regular updates on the progress of the project will allow both internal monitoring of the project as well as rapid dissemination of the achievements.

6.4 Social media

The project has social media presence on Twitter (<https://twitter.com/Catco2N>), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/catco2nvers>) and Youtube (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/Catco2nvers>) to ensure wider dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. Social media will be used as a tool to announce project developments, but most importantly drive traffic to the project website.

Twitter, LinkedIn, and Youtube accounts have been established and content related to CATCO2NVERS has been posted regularly beginning M1 to increase outreach.

For the first phase of the project, the social media accounts will share posts related to the project scope and post on events where CATCO2NVERS is to be presented to build a community of interest, creating an audience for when there are project results to share.

Online media platforms will be monitored to provide information on the analytics, sources, types of content, and individuals/organisations that promote or disseminate project messages, allowing optimisation and targeting of communication to ensure maximum outreach of news or results. These results will also be included in interim reports and the final dissemination report. The social media accounts will be managed by SIE with support from the partners.

Consortium partners will follow the project's social media channels and engage with them as much as possible. Whenever possible, the partners will share posts on their corporate websites and social media networks. If they need assistance, SIE can guide them on the best ways to do so.

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6.5 Printed materials

A poster, a factsheet, a roll-up, and a brochure have been developed for distribution to partner networks and at conferences, exhibitions, and other events. The first project poster and brochure version contain general information about the research activities, participants, and expected results. In addition, a general PowerPoint presentation has also been created, presenting the project's objectives, methodology, partners, etc.

Image 6.5.1: CATCO₂NVERS poster (left) and factsheet (right)

CATCO₂NVERS

The overall idea of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 5 added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMEs) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry, the project will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. To this end, the vision of the project revolves around two main axes:

- 1). Developing and applying catalyst-based technologies for CO₂ conversion to added-value chemicals
- 2). Validating technologies at TRL5 with industrial synthetic off-gases and providing sustainability and proving socioeconomic and industrial feasibility.

PROJECT PARTNERS

FUNCITEC, WAGENINGEN UR, CARTIF, CSIC, UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE, avantium, perseo, HYSYTECH, nova, Dan*no artificial nature, Sustainable INNOVATIONS, alchemia nova, AVA BIOCHEM, EVYAP, JM Johnson Matthey

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CATCO₂NVERS

- **DEVELOPMENT OF BREAKTHROUGH TECHNOLOGIES** FOR THE CONVERSION OF CO₂ INTO HIGH ADDED-VALUE CHEMICALS.
- **DEFINITION OF PROCESSES** TARGETS INCLUDING ENERGY REQUIREMENTS, PRODUCTION COSTS, AND YIELDS.
- **NEW BUSINESS MODELS** AND VALUE CHAINS IN THE CO₂ UTILISATION SECTOR.
- **DESIGN OF AN INTEGRATED PROCESS** WITH ZERO OR NEGATIVE GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS
- **DIVERSIFICATION** OF THE ECONOMIC BASE OF BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES BY 2030

CATCO₂NVERS @Catco2N www.catco2nvers.eu

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CATCO₂NVERS

Image 6.5.2: CATCO₂NVERS brochure

PROJECT PARTNERS

FUNDITEC
 WAGENINGEN
 CARTIF
 CSIC
 UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE
 avantium
 persea biotechnology
 HYSYTECH
 nova
 Dan*no artificial nature
 Sustainable INNOVATIONS
 alchemia
 AVA BIOCHEM
 EVYAP
 JM Johnson Matthey Inspiring science, enhancing life

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DESCRIPTION

The overall idea of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 5 added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMES) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry, the project will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

IMPACTS

CATCO₂NVERS will advance in setting up sound business models which involve all the actors across the proposed value chains and consider the different scenarios of the technology implementation while bringing down environmental impacts and production costs

- Development of breakthrough technologies for the conversion of CO₂ into high added-value chemicals. Definition of processes targets including energy requirements, production costs, and yields
- Design of an integrated process with zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions
- New business models and value chains in the CO₂ utilisation sector.
- Diversification of the economic base of bio-based industries by 2030

METHODOLOGY

WP1: CO₂ analysis and up-grading
 Leader: DLR/ITERIC; Tring: M1-8

WP2: Electrocatalytic conversion of CO₂ to glyoxylic acid
 Leader: AVANTUM; Tring: M1-20

WP3: Biocatalytic conversion of CO₂ to lactic acid
 Leader: WAGENINGEN; Tring: M1-19

WP4: Thermocatalytic conversion of CO₂ to platform chemicals (FDME, CCFAMES and Methanol)
 Leader: FUNDITEC; Tring: M1-30

WP5: Validation of technologies and added-value chemicals
 Leader: FUNDITEC; Tring: M15-46

WP6: Sustainability and circularity assessments
 Leader: NOVA; Tring: M15-48

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. To this end, the vision of the project revolves around two main axes:

- 1). Developing and applying catalyst-based technologies for CO₂ conversion to added-value chemicals
- 2). Validating technologies at TRL5 with industrial synthetic off-gases and providing sustainability and proofing socioeconomic and industrial feasibility.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 6.5.3: CATCO₂NVERS Roll-up

The roll-up banner features the CATCO₂NVERS logo at the top center. Below it, a grid of member logos is displayed, including FUNDiTEC, WAGENINGEN UR, CARTIF, CSIC, UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE, avantium, perseo biotechnology, HYSYTECH, nova, Dan*no artificial nature, Sustainable INNOVATIONS, alchemia nova, AVA BIOCHEM, EVYAP, and JM Johnson Matthey. The bottom section contains the website www.catco2nvers.eu, social media handles @Catco2N and CATCO2NVERS, and the Horizon 2020 European Union Funding logo. A small text box at the bottom right states: "Catco2nvers has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101000580."

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CATCO₂NVERS

Image 6.5.4: CATCO₂NVERS PowerPoint

6.6 Newsletter and press releases

Electronic newsletters will be prepared every 6 months and will include project updates, announcements, interviews, and other information related to CATCO₂NVERS, to be distributed to stakeholders and partner networks and posted on the project website. Moreover, project updates may appear in partners' respective newsletters, which are distributed electronically to their contacts within their specific industry.

Press releases will be published to announce newsworthy developments during the project. They will be written in English and sent to the European press and national journalists, with the help of the project partners.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 6.6: CATCO₂NVERS Press release

CATCO₂NVERS, a project that seeks to reduce greenhouse gas from the bio-based industries, kicks off

- CATCO₂NVERS is led by FUNDITEC and formed by fifteen partners from eight countries.
- CATCO₂NVERS has received €6,6 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

Madrid (Spain), May 27th, 2021. A European consortium is working on the implementation of CATCO₂NVERS, a new Horizon 2020 research and innovation project that kicked off this month and which aims to create added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies.

The consortium is formed by fifteen partners from eight European countries that will work for 48 months to bring the use of CO₂ for the production of chemicals a step closer to industrial implementation taking into account their market projection and public perception to support the European Union in becoming a global leader in CO₂ re-use technologies.

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from the biobased industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes (electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermochemical). **The project objective is to transform waste-CO₂ from two biobased industries into five added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furan dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters, and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics, and plastic industries.**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000580.

6.7 Scientific journals and trade magazines

At least eight scientific papers will be prepared by the technical and academic partners. The project's results will be published in international scientific journals and trade magazines, such as the Journal of CO₂ Utilization, Journal of the American Chemical Society, Journal of the American Chemical Society, ChemSusChem, Journal of Power Sources, International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, Energy and Fuels, Waste and Biomass Valorization, Green chemistry, Advanced materials, Journal of separation and purification technology, Biomass and Bioenergy and Catalysis today

6.8 Participation at conferences, workshops, and events

Project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, workshops, to meet target groups, other stakeholders, public authorities, and the scientific community and to raise awareness about the project objectives and results. These events provide access to target audiences at local, national, European, and international levels.

Conferences and trade fairs of interest identified for the CATCO₂NVERS project are as follows:

Table 6.9: List of events and conferences identified

EVENT	DAY	LOCATION	LINK
2nd Carbon Dioxide Conversion Catalysis	November 8-9 2021	Online	https://www.rsc.org/events/detail/47592/2nd-carbon-dioxide-conversion-catalysis-virtual-conference
11th International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Applications	November 20-21, 2021	Zurich	https://iccsea2021.org/
European Blockchain Convention	December 13-16, 2021	Online	https://eblockchainconvention.com/
Global Experts conference on Materials Science & Nanotechnology 2021	December 2-4, 2021	Amsterdam	https://www.mscholarconferences.com/GECMN21/6/home.html#organizers
International Conference on Cellulose Fibres	February 2-3, 2022	Cologne	https://cellulose-fibres.eu/
JEC World	March 8-10, 2022	Paris	https://www.jec-world.events/
Biofuel Intl. Conference & Expo	March 15-16, 2022	Brussels	https://biofuels-news.com/conference/biofuels/biofuels_index_2022.php
EUBCE: The Leading Platform for Global Biomass Innovation	May 9-13, 2022	Florence	https://www.eubce.com/
The Renewable Materials Conference	May 10-12, 2022	Cologne	https://renewable-materials.eu/

International Symposium on Relations between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Catalysis	June 26-29, 2022	Oslo	https://www.mn.uio.no/ishhc19
Renewable, resources and biorefineries	June 8-10, 2022	Ghent	https://rbcconference.com/news/
XXII International Symposium on Homogeneous Catalysis	July 24-29, 2022	Lisbon	https://xxii-ishc.events.chemistry.pt/
Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference 2022	October 25-27, 2022	Espoo	https://ispt.eu/events/nordic-wood-biorefinery-conference/ https://www.vitresearch.com/en/news-and-ideas/nordic-wood-biorefinery-conference-2022
ECOMONDO	November 8-11, 2022	Rimini	https://www.showsbee.com/fairs/77889-Ecomondo-Rimini-2022.html

At the end of the project, a final conference will be organised where the partners will present the project results and perspectives to relevant stakeholders from the industry, the scientific community, regulatory bodies, and others with an interest in the field. The presentations will analyse and reflect upon the developments of CATCO2NVERS. Industry events are also contemplated to spread knowledge on the project upbringings.

7 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The social media activities will start as the project kicks off while the website waits to be activated. The publications and conferences presentations will take place as the project progresses and be published in the relevant locations on the website.

Publications and conference presentations are subject to project IP policy. Dissemination activities can be delayed as securing the business interests of any partner needs to be considered first.

The developed dissemination strategy will be continuously updated to ensure the maximum measurable project impact is achieved and the project website will be the central tool to track the progressive efficacy of the communication efforts.

Ambitious CATCO2NVERS indicators have been established :

Table 7.1: Indicators and targets

CATCO2NVERS

Tool/ Channel	Indicator	Target Number	Information Source
Brochure Leaflet Poster, Roll Up	N° of copies distributed	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders
Project Website	Number of visits	Visits per year: <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics
Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Number of followers Number of impressions Engagement rate	Twitter; (a) Followers: < 50 poor; 50 – 100 good;> 150 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn; (a) Followers: <50 poor; 50 – 100 good; >150 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2- 3% good; >3% excellent	Social media analytics
Videos	Number of views	At least 2 in the project. Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	Website / YouTube Analytics
Newsletter	Subscriber & Readers	1500 views (500 subscribers x 3 Newsletter)	Recording of e-mail sent, website download, analytics
Press Releases	Number of media stakeholders addressed Number of views on the website and social media	25 Media stakeholder; 1000 views per Press Release	Recording of e-mails sent, Media list, consulting media website
Scientific Publications	Number of Publications	8 scientific papers	Consulting site where publication is placed Contemplate ResearchGate as a platform
CATCO2NVERS Workshops	Number of attendees	3 EU workshop (M24, M30 & M36) 100 attendees	Registration list

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CATCO2NVERS Webinars		2 Webinars x 10 participants (from M30)	Registration List
Conferences	Number of conferences attended	12 Conferences 1800 participants (12 conferences x 150 participants)	Registration List
Trade Fairs	Number of trade fairs attended	6 trade fairs 30000 participants (6 trade fair x 5000 participants)	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information, Business Trade fairs Cards exchanged

8 Levels of dissemination

Key targets groups operate at different geographic levels, which will influence which communication tools and media will be employed.

8.1 European level – EC

The European Commission will be informed about the results via the periodic reporting of the project (mid-term review, minutes of periodical meetings, updates of this document) in order to modify related regulations if necessary and to propose collaboration with other ongoing projects on dissemination activities.

8.2 International level – Industry, scientific community

The relevant international organisations will be informed of the results. Scientific knowledge can be translated into practical information, guidelines, and regulatory policies.

Direct mailing to specific organisations and stakeholders will be used to distribute electronic resources to raise public awareness.

Technical journals, conferences and workshops at both national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be used for the dissemination of knowledge both at research and industrial levels.

9 Methodology

The following internal and external communication activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterward to ensure that the results of CATCO2NVERS are efficiently and effectively communicated to the project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

9.1 Internal communication

Effective internal communication is key to sharing information and ensuring that the deliverables are met. Therefore, regular face-to-face meetings and conference calls will take place to exchange project information, update progress, and share results. Consortium and technical meetings will take place two times a year, while Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing services will be used to facilitate collaboration within WPs.

Apart from specific emails, taking advantage of the at least 6-monthly meetings, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and streamline a content curation process. This will allow the partners to take a more focused and systematic approach, strengthening actions taken to communicate and report on the project. A delegate from all consortium partners of CATCO2NVERS will attend this meeting.

To facilitate efficient communication among partners, SIE will create a section within the website that will link to the project documentation and data exchange SharePoint created by the project coordinator FUNDITEC. This platform will host project materials for internal use, including regular updates on the project development, a project calendar, meeting documents (agendas, minutes, and presentations), manuscripts in progress, and project reports. The platform will have a content management system, allowing all partners to upload content themselves.

9.2 External communication

Every effort will be made to publicize the work of the consortium via the media, publications, conference presentations, trade fairs, and workshops, as well as through the Commission and industry bodies. Results of the project will be disseminated via reports, scientific papers, and technical articles. All public communication, and in particular scientific publications, will be made open access, to facilitate scientific exchange.

All project partners are expected to support dissemination, to ensure that stakeholders will be engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. Partners' activities may include

but are not limited to: engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to SIE's inputs on social media, proactively sharing information with SIE about project results, listing their communication activities in a shared file, and providing SIE with translations of lay materials in their local language. Where possible, partners will translate press releases into their national languages and keep SIE informed about plans, by creating lists of national media channels they will try to reach.

10 Timeline

As the project has different development phases, the communication focus would be different across each of them.

10.1 Phase I: Awareness phase

The first phase of the project is the Pre-Development phase. It will take place during the first year of the project, from M1 to M18. No results have been generated yet, so the main communication activities will focus on raising awareness about the project, its objectives, and expected impacts. This will be done by making use of the project identity developed that includes the project logo and graphical visual identity; promoting the project website among stakeholders, and distributing communication and dissemination material such as the project's brochure. It is also key to identify the relevant stakeholders for CATCO₂NVERS as well as to establish contact with similar initiatives. In this phase, the consortium partners will also participate in relevant events and conferences, will build strong networking relationships, and will contribute as well to the communication actions.

10.2 Phase II: Knowledge transfer

The second phase (M12-M36) aims to provide the different stakeholders with the first results of the project and to raise interest in the upcycling capacity of products and materials. The first workshops, webinars, and technical papers will start to be produced.

10.3 Phase III: Replication and exploitation

The third phase (M36-M54) consists of supporting the replication and exploitation actions of CATCO₂NVERS. With the project coming to an end, it will be essential to link the exploitation and dissemination activities to guarantee the future replication of

results. The final event will be celebrated openly during this period and all the knowledge and materials gathered in the project life will be made available online.

11 Actions M1-M6

11.1 Project identity and materials

In the first phase of the project, a visual identity for CATCO₂NVERS was created. It included the logo of the project, and the brand guidelines (typography, colours, iconography, photography style). Different communication materials were also developed, including a brochure, a roll-up, a poster, and a project presentation. A template for the deliverables, a word document template, and a PowerPoint template was produced and shared with the partners.

The first brochure, poster, factsheet, roll-up, and project presentation were produced and made available on the website of the project as soon as it was operative: <https://catco2nvers.eu/documents/>

Image 11.1.1: CATCO₂NVERS Word Template

Title 1

1 Title 2

1.1 Title 3

1.1.1 Subtitle 1

1.1.1.1 Subtitle 2

Text: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

11.2 Press Releases

A press release was launched at the beginning of the project. It was sent to approximately 200 local and trade media by SIE and several consortium partners.

It was published in more than 10 different media outlets, including Cordis, the partner's websites and social media, and trade media. Likewise, it was also uploaded to the CATCO2NVERS website.

Table 11.2.1: Media and partners publications

Media	Link
RETEMA	https://www.retema.es/noticia/catco2nvers-un-proyecto-que-busca-reducir-los-gei-de-las-industrias-de-base-biologica-Zl05m
CORDIS	https://cordis.europa.eu/article/rcn/430167_en.html
InterEmpresas	https://www.interempresas.net/Plastico/Articulos/352727-Dan-na-pone-marcha-planta-piloto-produccion-bioplasticos-sector-biomedico-tecno.html
Parc Científic de Barcelona	https://www.pcb.ub.edu/en/danna-pone-en-marcha-una-planta-piloto-de-produccion-de-biomateriales-en-el-pcb/
Partner	Link
FUNDITEC	https://funditec.es/funditec-suma-4-nuevos-proyectos-europeos-ademas-de-ser-responsable-de-la-coordinacion-de-uno-de-ellos/
SIE	https://sustainableinnovations.eu/catco2nvers-project-reduce-greenhouse-gas-co2/
AVT	https://www.avantium.com/press-releases/avantium-awarded-e178-million-in-total-from-eu-grants-for-the-development-of-electrochemical-processes-and-co2-based-polymers/
CARTIF	https://www.cartif.es/en/catco2nvers-en/
CARTIF	https://www.cartif.es/en/catco2nvers-reduce-greenhouse-gases-biobased-industries/

CATCO₂NVERS

CARTIF + FUNDITEC	https://atlastecnologico.com/hacia-la-economia-circular-de-la-mano-de-los-centros-tecnologicos-siete-iniciativas-transformadoras/
ALC	https://www.alchemia-nova.net/projects/catco2nvers/
WR	https://research.wur.nl/en/projects/eu-21025-catco2nvers-creating-added-value-chemicals-from-bio-indu
HYSYTECH	https://www.hysytech.com/News/catco2nvers-kom-eng
EMI	https://www.emi-twente.nl/emi-twente-is-proud-to-participate-in-catco2nvers/

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 11.2: Example of publication

CATCO₂NVERS

European Commission | CORDIS | English | Search

HOME | RESEARCHERS | BUSINESS OPPORTUNITIES | NEWS & MEDIA | PROJECTS & RESULTS | ABOUT US | LOGIN

News

CATCO₂NVERS, a project that seeks to reduce greenhouse gas from the bio-based industries, kicks off

CATCO₂NVERS is led by FUNDITEC and formed by fifteen partners from eight countries. CATCO₂NVERS has received €6.6 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

NEW PRODUCTS AND TECHNOLOGIES

© CATCO₂NVERS

Madrid (Spain), May 27th, 2021. A European consortium is working on the implementation of CATCO₂NVERS, a new Horizon 2020 research and innovation project that kicked off this month and which aims to create added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies.

The consortium is formed by fifteen partners from eight European countries that will work for 18 months to bring the use of CO₂ for the production of chemicals a step closer to industrial implementation taking into account their market projection and public perception to support the European Union in becoming a global leader in CO₂-reuse technologies.

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from the bio-based industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes (electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermochemical). The project objective is to transform waste-CO₂ from two bio-based industries into five added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furic dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated tery acid methyl ester, and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetic, and plastic industries.

CATCO₂NVERS will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions, which will contribute to setting up sound business models involving all the value chain stakeholders and bringing down environmental impacts and production costs.

In summary, CATCO₂NVERS is focused on reducing industrial CO₂ emissions while exploring new procedures to produce bioproducts. With this aim, a bottom-up approach is used by the design and development of innovative catalytic technologies for the valorisation of CO₂ in the fabrication of different bio-based products, including monomers for bioplastics production, using CO₂ streams from biorefineries.

About CATCO₂NVERS

Coordinated by Foundation for Development and Technological Innovation (FUNDITEC), CATCO₂NVERS is formed by Aicheira-roca, Avantium Chemicals B.V., DAN'NA Artificial Marine, CARTIF, CSIC, EVRYAR University of Twente, AXA Biochem, Hysitech, Nova-Institut, Johnson Matthey, PERSEO Biotechnology, Stichting Wageningen Research, and Sustainable Innovations.

The project has received €6.6 million funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101000580.

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Related projects

PROJECT

CATCO₂NVERS
Creating added-value chemicals from bio-industrial CO₂ emissions using integrated catalytic technologies
10 September 2021

Last update: 30 June 2021
Record number: 430147
 My Booklet

CATCO₂NVERS

11.3 Conferences attended

The CATCO₂NVERS consortium partners were encouraged to participate actively in the communication and dissemination actions and, as part of that, attendance at events, conferences, and shows is one of the main activities of the strategy. However, due to COVID-19 restrictions the participation in conferences and events has been low. Nevertheless, a list of upcoming events has been identified as displayed in Table 6.9 where partners will be encouraged to participate.

CATCO₂NVERS has been showcased in the PTECO₂ conference where the project coordinator spoke about the project to internal and external audiences.

The session was recorded and uploaded to CATCO₂NVERS's YouTube account and also to the website.

11.4 Social Media

The social media accounts on Twitter <https://twitter.com/Catco2N> LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/catco2nvers/> and Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/CATCO2NVERS> were set up at the beginning of the project and inaugurated with content on the kick-off meeting.

During this period, we shared 21 publications, achieved 78 followers, and our publications reached a total of 14,9K impressions on Twitter, as of October 13th.

Image 11.4.1: Twitter Account

CATCO₂NVERS

We began the activity on LinkedIn on August 31st, 2021. In this period, and until September 30th, we have published 21 posts and achieved 140 followers. The publications reached more than 13.500 impressions.

Image 11.4.2: LinkedIn Account

Additionally, a video has been uploaded to CATCO2NVERS's YouTube channel

Image 11.4.3: YouTube channel

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CATCO₂NVERS

11.5 Newsletter

The first newsletter of CATCO₂NVERS' project was released on September 28th and published on the [website](#).

Image 11.5.1: Newsletter 1

NEWSLETTER 1 | SEPTEMBER 2021

CATCO₂NVERS, A PROJECT THAT SEEKS TO REDUCE GREENHOUSE GAS FROM THE BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES, KICKS OFF

KICK-OFF MEETING
From 8 to 9 June

Transforming waste-CO₂ into 5 added-value chemicals with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry

CATCO₂NVERS consortium members were reunited to present the future work each one is going to develop to achieve the goals of the project.

During the teleconference, hosted by [FUNDITEC](#), the partners were able to explain their future responsibilities within the project, as well as to show their corporate presentations.

The core purpose of CATCO₂NVERS is to **reduce greenhouse gas emissions** (GHG) from the biobased industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes.

The consortium is formed by **fifteen partners** from eight European countries that will work for 48 months to bring the use of CO₂ for the production of chemicals a step closer to industrial implementation

[READ MORE](#)

HAVE YOU ALREADY SEEN THE CATCO₂NVERS MATERIALS?

We have prepared a set of **dissemination materials** to raise the awareness about our project objectives and goals. Download them by clicking below

[DOWNLOAD NOW](#)

CATCO₂NVERS AT THE PTECO₂ TECHNICAL WEBINAR

On June 22, the [Spanish CO₂ Technology Platform](#) (PTECO₂) counted on the presence of CATCO₂NVERS project. There, [Dulce Muñoz](#), Scientific & Technical Manager from [FUNDITEC](#), showcased CATCO₂NVERS, on behalf of the consortium, the project scope, and approach under the topic of **catalytic conversion of CO₂ into chemical intermediates of industrial value**.

PTECO₂ webinar was held virtually in Spanish language in collaboration with [AEI](#) and [INCAR-CSIC](#). The session was structured in several lectures delivered by recognised speakers, both from academia and industry, in the framework of the **potential uses and transformations of CO₂ in Spain**.

[WATCH NOW](#)

CATCO₂NVERS IMPACTS & METHODOLOGY

Development of breakthrough technologies for the conversion of CO₂ into high added-value chemicals. Definition of processes targets including energy requirements, production costs, and yields.

Design of an integrated process with zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

New business models and value chains in the CO₂ utilisation sector.

Diversification of the economic base of bio-based industries by 2030.

CATCO₂NVERS PARTNERS

Coordinated by Foundation for Development and Technological Innovation (FUNDITEC), CATCO₂NVERS is formed by Alchemia-nova, AVA Biochem, Avantium Chemicals BV, CARTIF, CSIC, DAN*NA Artificial Nature, EVYAP, University of Twente, Hysytech, Nova-Institute, Johnson Matthey, PERSEO Biotechnology, Sustainable Innovations and Wageningen Food & Biobased Research.

VISIT OUR WEBSITE AND FOLLOW ON SOCIAL MEDIA!

We will be posting all the project developments, actions and news on our website and social media channels. Follow us to make sure you do not miss anything out!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000580

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CATCO₂NVERS

11.6 Website

The website <https://catco2nvers.eu/> was launched on June 25th (M2) with essential information of the project that will be updated constantly with progress and news from the project and partners.

Image 11.6.1: CATCO₂NVERS website

WHAT IS CATCO₂NVERS?

The overall idea of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the bio-based industries transforming waste CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 3 added-value chemicals: glycolic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAME) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry, the project will produce bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

DISCOVER THE PARTNERS

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of CATCO₂NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. To this end, the vision of the project revolves around two main axes:

NEWS

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11.6.1 Website analytics

Since the website has been operative until 12/10/2021, it has accounted for 2.370 visits and the average time that a user spends on it is 5:38 minutes. These numbers are very good and indicate that the project is getting very qualified website traffic.

Figure 11.6.1: Web analytics. Source: Google Analytics

Figure 11.6.2: Website top locals

12 Actions M7-M18

This section corresponds to the update of the Communication & Dissemination Plan D7.2 (M6) led by SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE). Throughout this section, a complete description of the activities carried out during the month 7 (M7) to month 18 (M18) period in terms of Communication and Dissemination will be further explained.

Likewise, the Communication and Dissemination strategy for the upcoming period will be included. All partners contributed to dissemination and communication activities in line with the aims and goals of the plan.

12.1 Project identity and materials

At the beginning of the project, CATCO₂NVERS produced a series of printed documents (brochure, poster, factsheet, and roll-up) to be distributed at the events attended by partners.

As the COVID-19 restrictions have been lifted SIE handled during the first face-to-face General Assembly meeting a set of 30 brochures per partner. A total of 450 brochures were distributed to the partners in order to disseminate the project when participating in events, trade fairs or conferences.

Image 12.1.1: Printed materials in the General Assembly Meeting

From its side, SIE handled FUNDITEC the official roll-up of the project as the coordination organised in M15 a conference about catalytic solutions for a sustainable industry. In addition to this event, FUNDITEC also used the printed materials in other events such as the 20th International Zeolite Conference.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 12.1.2: Marcelo Echeverri (researcher at FUNDITEC) at the 20th International Zeolite Conference in a poster presentation holding a set of CATCO₂NVERS brochures

For their part, NOVA also handled several brochures at the Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels and Chemicals:

Image 12.1.3: Matthias Stratmann (Head of Sustainability at NOVA) at the Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels and Chemicals

Furthermore, partners are encouraged to share with stakeholders the online versions, made available on the website of the roll-up, brochure, factsheet, project presentation and poster.

12.2 Conferences attended

As mentioned in the 12.7 section, due to some of the suspensions of the COVID-19 restrictions, the CATCO2NVERS consortium has been able to attend more than ten conferences, events and trade fairs in the framework of a wide variety of areas such as cosmetic, pharma sector, R&D, plastic sector, among others:

- [SusPlast Event](#) – October 2021, CSIC. Keynote lecture
- [InnoFUTURO Conference](#) – November 2021, PERSEO. Keynote Lecture
- [X CM-10 Macromolecules Colloquium](#) – December 2021, CSIC. Online presentation.
- [International Seminar Biotechnology Applied to the Plastic Sector](#) – March 2022, PERSEO. Poster presentation.
- [Conference on Co2-Based Fuels and Chemicals](#) – March 2022, NOVA. Stakeholders engagement.
- [11th Conference of the framework program for research and innovation of the European Union, "The New Horizon for Europe"](#) – April 2022, FUNDITEC. Poster presentation.
- [Cosmofarma Exhibition](#) – May 2022, EVYAP. Stakeholders engagement.
- [GEPSAL 2022 Conference, Europe Day and Event in the Materials Physics Center](#) – May 2022, CSIC. Keynote lecture.
- [International Trade Fair Cosmetic Business 2022](#) – June 2022, EVYAP. Stakeholders engagement.
- [17th International Cosmetics, Beauty, Hair Exhibition: Beautyeurasia](#) – June 2022, EVYAP. Stakeholders engagement.
- [20th International Zeolite Conference](#) – July 2022, FUNDITEC. Poster presentation.

12.3 Events organised

Following the phases described in the [Timeline section](#) of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, no events were foreseen during the awareness phase (M1-M12) of the project. As M18, the project is now in the knowledge transfer phase where the first workshops, webinars, and technical papers will start to be produced. For their part, FUNDITEC organised a conference in the framework of [catalytic solutions for a sustainable industry](#). The session was celebrated in collaboration with JM, CSIC who

CATCO₂NVERS

introduced also some of the sister initiatives of CATCO₂NVERS: [FRACTION](#) and [CO₂SMOS](#).

12.4 Interaction with EU projects

Clustering, with other EU-related initiatives, is also an important part of the communication and dissemination of the project. SIE started to reach some of these initiatives in M9 and successfully could organise an [internal call](#) in M10 to start seeking new synergies and potential collaborations. The call was led by SIE. The CATCO₂NVERS project engaged with the [CO₂SMOS](#) and [VIVALDI](#) projects which are under the same European topic "Bio-based industries leading the way in turning carbon dioxide emissions into chemicals".

Image 12.4.1: The CATCO₂NVERS Project explores new related projects to collaborate with under the bio-based industries leading the way in turning carbon dioxide emissions into chemicals topic

During the session, the CO₂SMOS project explained its role to transform the carbon emissions generated from bioprocesses into different sustainable bioproducts; VIVALDI showcased its approach how to converting off-gas emissions from bio-based Industries into CO₂-based chemicals; for their part, the CATCO₂NVERS project presented the concept to reduce greenhouse gasses emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 5 added-value chemicals.

12.5 Social Media

The social media channels were put in place at the beginning of the project. In the following section, a description of the performance is conducted in terms of number of followers, number of posts, engagement rate levels as well as graphics and analytics.

12.5.1 LinkedIn

CATCO₂NVERS's presence on LinkedIn has reached 285 followers by M18 after 56 updates. The engagement rate in this platform (number of interactions with post-likes, comments, shares) has reached 5,20% (more than 2% is considered excellent performance).

The number of impressions (views) from M6 to M18 is around 30000.

Image 12.5.1.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn profile. This data does not reflect the October analytics)

Metrics

12.5.2 Twitter

As of October 2022, CATCO₂NVERS has 210 followers on this social media channel after 56 updates. The content on the profile has generated more than 18000 views from M6 to M18. The current engagement rate for Twitter is 3,12% (higher than 0,5% is considered great performance).

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M7-M9

Your Tweets earned **6.6K impressions** over this **91 day period**

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M10-M12

Your Tweets earned **6.4K impressions** over this **89 day period**

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M13-M15

Your Tweets earned **2.7K impressions** over this **89 day period**

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 12.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M16-M18 (Data of this quarter is not entirely reflected)

Your Tweets earned **2.4K impressions** over this **59 day** period

12.5.3 YouTube

At least two videos were expected to be produced along with the project's lifetime. To date, CATCO₂NVERS has uploaded two videos reaching more than 200 views in total. The official video of the project was uploaded in M9. SIE will upload the audio-visual content when generating (recordings of workshops, posters presentations, etc.)

Image 12.5.3.1: CATCO₂NVERS videos on YouTube

12.6 Newsletters

As mentioned in the Grant Agreement, it is expected that eight newsletters would be released during the project life. The first newsletter (M5) included the main information of the project such as the methodology, impacts, and partners as well as the first press release and the communication materials. CATCO₂NVERS's second newsletter (M11)

CATCO₂NVERS

contained information about the first general assembly meeting, information on the new collaboration with the related projects CO2SMOS and VIVALDI, events attended, the official project video, and partners interviews.

The third newsletter (M17) contained the relevant actions carried out in the last semester of the project such as the upcoming general assembly plus the second general assembly meeting, the two technical milestones achieved, all the conferences and events attended as well as two more partners interviews.

As of M18, the Newsletter has 107 subscribers and an average of 40 readers per Newsletter. The Newsletters are also uploaded to the Documents section on the CATCO₂NVERS website. From there, users can easily access each Newsletter and subscribe to receive upcoming ones.

Image 12.6.1: Documents Section: CATCO₂NVERS Newsletters

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 12.6.1: Newsletter 2 (left side) Newsletter 3 (right side).

NEWSLETTER 2 | MARCH 2022

CATCO₂NVERS HOLDS ITS FIRST GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEETING

GENERAL ASSEMBLY
NOVEMBER 5, 2021
CATCO₂NVERS

The CATCO₂NVERS project held its first **General Assembly** meeting on 5 November in a hybrid way where some partners could attend physically while others were connected via teleconference. The session was celebrated at **FUNDITEC'S** facilities in Madrid, Spain.

During the meeting, the consortium partners exposed the advancement of each work package as well as discussed the next actions for the upcoming semester

[READ MORE](#)

CATCO₂NVERS EXPLORES NEW SYNERGIES WITH VIVALDI AND CO₂SMOS PROJECTS

On February 3rd, 2022, the CATCO₂NVERS project held an online meeting together with the initiatives **CO₂SMOS** and **VIVALDI** to explore future collaborations under the framework of bio-based industries leading the way in turning carbon dioxide emissions

The core of the session was to introduce the **project's scope** and share some of the **best practices** to collaborate. With the strong competencies of the three projects, CATCO₂NVERS, CO₂SMOS, and VIVALDI will be able to boost the development of turning carbon

NEWSLETTER 3 | SEPTEMBER 2022

CATCO₂NVERS WILL HOLD ITS THIRD GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEETING

On November 2022, the CATCO₂NVERS consortium partners will meet in Istanbul, Turkey to discuss the latest progress and advancements carried out in the last semester. Hosted by **EVYAP**, the partners will have the opportunity to establish synergies, collaborations as well as to define future actions for the next period. Have a look at the previous General Assembly meeting celebrated in the Netherlands.

[READ MORE](#)

CATCO₂NVERS ACHIEVES TWO MILESTONES

The **University of Twente** has created a report detailing the most reasonable routes for upgrading the CO₂ streams. It started with the reports delivered by our project partners, **Avantium** and **PERSEO**, who shared information about the composition of their CO₂-rich streams. With all that information, the University of Twente compared those compositions and established that the first was a typical post-combustion CO₂ stream, while the other was similar to that obtained from an oxy-combustion process.

The CATCO₂NVERS consortium has worked on the analysis of the compositions of the two gas streams at **PERSEO** and **Avantium** and the definition of the two synthetic gas compositions for demonstration of the technologies.

CARTIF has determined the trace element limits of industrial gas streams for the methanol production process. For this purpose, **CARTIF** has used the composition of the different gases provided by **PERSEO** and **Avantium** and has determined the possible undesired effects on the catalyst performance.

[READ MORE](#)

CATCO₂NVERS

Since the official release of the website on M2, CATCO₂NVERS partners have contributed widely to its update by providing information on milestones, giving interviews, consolidating dissemination materials, etc.

As a living platform, the website has evolved from M6 to M18 to include all the relevant actions, news, articles and relevant documents developed within the CATCO₂NVERS framework.

Regarding the News section, in the last semester 23 blog posts have been published:

- [Interview with Alchemia Nova](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS holds its first General Assembly Meeting](#)
- [Interview with AVANTIUM](#)
- [Interview with CSIC](#)
- [SusPlast Event](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS explores new related projects to collaborate](#)
- [InnoFUTURO Conference](#)
- [X CM-10 Macromolecules Colloquium](#)
- [International Seminar Biotechnology Applied to the Plastic Sector](#)
- [Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels and Chemicals](#)
- [11th Conference of the framework program for research and innovation of the European Union, "The New Horizon for Europe"](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS, the progress after one year of running](#)
- [Interview with CARTIF](#)
- [Cosmofarma Exhibition](#)
- [GEPSAL 2022 Conference, Europe Day and Event in the Materials Physics Center](#)
- [Catco₂nvers achieves a new milestone: Theoretical Route for CO₂ Upgrading](#)
- [International Trade Fair Cosmetic Business 2022](#)
- [Catco₂nvers achieves a new milestone: Analysis of the compositions of the two gas streams and definition of the two synthetic gas compositions](#)
- [FUNDITEC organises a conference about catalytic solutions for a sustainable industry](#)

- [17th International Cosmetics, Beauty, Hair Exhibition: Beautyeurasia](#)
- [20th International Zeolite Conference](#)
- [Interview with DAN*NA](#)

Likewise, during this period the following documents have been uploaded to the CATCO₂NVERS website:

- [D7.1 Project Website](#)
- [D7.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan](#)
- [Newsletter 1](#)
- [Newsletter 2](#)
- [Newsletter 3](#)

From M7 to M18 the CATCO₂NVERS website has gained around 1000 unique visitors with an average session duration of 02:45 minutes which means that the audience is very engaged with the content of the website.

During the last month, SIE started to design a new tracking system to evaluate the performance of the website. Due to the new Google Analytics software and updates, the system used until now will be obsoleted to monitor the upcoming periods. For that reason, SIE will explore different routes through Google Analytics 4 (GA4).

12.8 Partners contribution

As stated in the Grant Agreement Article 29 "Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — 'disseminate' its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium)."

In compliance with this article, our partners have actively contributed to disseminating the CATCO₂NVERS project from the very beginning by different means: social media posts, attendance at conferences and shows, email campaigns, newsletters, press releases, etc. to good effect.

CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn posts have been shared more than 100 times from M7-M18 and the partners were very supportive in this area. Likewise, consortium members have also made different posts during M7-M18 about CATCO₂NVERS plus reported the social media post from CATCO₂NVERS social media channels.

CATCO₂NVERS

Some partners have accounts on other media channels and they have disseminated the project as well over there. The full partner's contribution is listed in the dissemination tables (Annex 1).

13 Actions M19-M30

This section corresponds to the update of the Communication & Dissemination Plan D7.2 (M6) led by SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE). Throughout this section, a complete description of the activities carried out during the month 19 (M19) to month 30 (M30) period in terms of Communication and Dissemination will be further explained.

Likewise, the Communication and Dissemination strategy for the upcoming period will be included. All partners contributed to dissemination and communication activities in line with the aims and goals of the plan.

13.1 Project identity and materials

During the period reported (M19-M30) the partners have distributed several communication materials produced by SIE at the beginning of the project such as the roll-up and brochures.

On June 6, 2023, our partner University of Twente organised an Open House event for young and old people curious about science and technology. Most of the communication materials were showcased during the activity including the project roll-up, brochures, and the official video among others.

Image 13.1.1: University of Twente Open House Event.

Additionally, other scientific communication materials were produced by the technical partners such as poster presentations. In December 2023, Wageningen University & Research showcased CATCO₂NVERS during the NVBMB (The Dutch society for biochemistry and molecular biology) through a poster presentation where

the concept, methodology, impact and objectives of the project were explained under the topic “The expanding world of biological one-carbon fixation – made by nature & engineers”.

Image 13.1.2: Daan van Vliet (WUR) in the NVBMB event

On May 11, 2023, our technical project coordinator Dulce Muñoz, researcher in FUNDITEC, introduced the CATCO₂NVERS project during the Spanish conference entitled “adding value to CO₂” organised by PTECO₂ and SUSCHEM ES in Bilbao, Spain. Additionally, Eva Maya from CSIC contributed to disseminating the CATCO₂NVERS project by presenting two posters with FUNDITEC.

Image 13.1.3: Dulce Muñoz (FUNDITEC) in the PTECO₂ event.

Finally, on March 1-2, 2023 our entity coordinator FUNDITEC attended again together with CSIC, the VIII International Seminar of Bioplastics and Sustainable Composites in Valencia, Spain where they showcased the initiative through a poster presentation in

CATCO₂NVERS

the framework of CO₂ thermocatalytic conversions that give rise to useful intermediates in biopolymers synthesis.

Image 13.1.4: Poster presented at the VIII International Seminar of Bioplastics and Sustainable Composites

Furthermore, partners have been encouraged again to share with stakeholders the online versions, made available on the website as well as sharing them on social media.

Image 13.1.4: Example of social media post sharing the CATCO₂NVERS poster.

Last but not least, new communication materials have been designed in collaboration with the related projects CO₂SMOS and VIVALDI with the aim of explaining the

importance of Europe leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals to a non-scientific audience.

Image 14.1.5: Example of social media post sharing the CATCO₂NVERS poster.

More information about the clustering can be found in the [13.4 section: Interaction with other EU projects](#).

13.2 Conferences attended

In the current period, the partners attended ten conferences and events to disseminate the CATCO₂NVERS project. Most of the events listed below have been properly disseminated on the project website as well as social media (hyperlinks are included):

- [15th European congress on catalysis](#). August 2023, CSIC. Keynote lecture.
- [The Netherlands Process Technology Symposium](#), July 2023, EMI. Keynote lecture.
- [International Congress on Membranes and Membrane Processes](#), July 2023 EMI. Keynote lecture.
- [Biennial Meeting of the Spanish Catalysis Society](#), June 2023. Poster presentation.
- [PTECO₂ Event](#). May, 2023. FUNDITEC and CSIC. Keynote lecture and poster presentation.

- Conference on CO₂-Based Fuels & Chemicals. April 2023, FUNDITEC. Keynote lecture.
- Stakeholder dialogue on the circular economy: from research to implementation, April 2023, ALCHEMIA NOVA. Keynote lecture and stakeholders' engagement.
- VIII International Seminar Of Bioplastics And Sustainable Composites, March 2023, FUNDITEC, CSIC. Poster presentation.
- NVBMB Fall Meeting, December 2022, Wageningen. Poster presentation.
- 18th Aachener Membran Kolloquium, November 2022, EMI. Trade fair and stakeholder engagement.

Image 13.2: Example of website event creativities:

13.3 Events organised

As M18, the project is now in the knowledge transfer phase where the first workshops, webinars, and technical papers started to be produced.

SIE and EMI collaborated together to disseminate the project to a non-scientific audience taking the advance of the University Of Twente Open House 2023. The session included a wide variety of activities such as workshops, guided tours, quizzes, and demonstrations where children and young students were able to learn about the initiative. Children were also allowed to create their membranes, adding an

CATCO₂NVERS

interactive element to the event. Most of the communication materials were showcased during the activity including the project roll-up, brochures, and the official video among others.

Image 13.3.1: Images of the EMI Open House 2023.

In this context, our partner CSIC also organised an event in the framework of Schuman Declaration from May 8 to May 10, 2023 that brought together young students and researchers working within the European scientific community. The goal was to showcase the research conducted within the European framework and highlight the opportunities that the European Union provides for participation, promotion, and funding across diverse fields such as biology, materials science, chemistry, physics, and more. Beatriz Fuerte Diez, PhD student at CSIC, showcased the CATCO₂NVERS project among the general public, including young students and children. Its objectives and accomplishments were shared to raise awareness and understanding of the project's importance in tackling carbon dioxide conversion.

Image 13.3.2: Commemorating the Schuman Declaration. Event organised by CSIC.

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

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CATCO2NVERS

Finally, as part of the interaction with other EU initiatives, SIE organised a joint webinar in collaboration with CO2SMOS and VIVALDI in the framework of Leading the way in turning CO2 emissions into chemicals where more than one hundred attendees enjoyed and learnt about the ambition, objectives, impacts, methodologies and concepts of each initiative showcased. The online webinar presented the different technologies and workflows in each project for turning CO2 into chemicals and it was opened to anyone who wanted to learn more about these initiatives and the different carbon capture methods and conversions.

Image 13.3.3: Screenshot during the webinar Leading the way in turning CO2 emissions into chemicals.

13.4 Interaction with EU projects

In the clustering meetings with CO2SMOS and VIVALDI reported during the M7 – M18, the three initiatives started to define joint activities to maximise impacts and engage with the different target audiences.

As explained in the previous section 13.1 Project identity and materials, one of the joint actions was to develop a joint handbook with an user-friendly design explaining the importance of Europe Leading the way in turning CO2 emissions into chemicals as well as the ambition behind the three related projects since all of them share a common topic. SIE develop the format, content, and layout of this document while COSMOS and VIVALDI introduced their project information.

The first part of the handbook is focused on providing a clear explanation of the need to investigate carbon capture utilisation. In this context, the objectives and impact of

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CATCO2NVERS

the three projects are explained concerning this theme. The second part of the handbook aims not only to explain and define easily the concept, objectives and processes of the three initiatives but also to give a comprehensive definition of the keywords that difficult for a non-scientific audience to understand the whole project. For that purpose, a YES, BUT... approach was conducted creating a double page where the user can easily do a deeper look at the technical concepts such as *catalytic process*, *bio-based industry*, etc.

Image 13.4.1: Example of double page of the joint handbook.

2. The ambition of three European Solutions

2.1 CATCO2NVERS

The overall idea of CATCO2NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gases emissions from the Bio-Based Industries transforming waste-CO₂ from 2 bio-based Industries into 5 added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid (GA), lactic acid (LA), furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME), cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMEs) and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics and plastic industry. The project will process bio-based products replacing fossil material with a zero or negative greenhouse gas emissions.

OBJECTIVES

- Developing and applying catalyst-based technologies for CO₂ conversion to added-value chemicals.
- Validating technologies with industrial synthetic off-gases and providing sustainability and proofing socioeconomic and industrial feasibility.

PROCESS

The core purpose of CATCO2NVERS is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the biobased industry by developing five innovative and integrated technologies based on three catalytic processes (electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermochemical).

The project aim is to transform waste-CO₂ from two biobased industries into five added-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furan dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters, and bio-methanol, with application in the chemical, cosmetics, and plastic industries.

YES, BUT....

What is a Bio-Based Industry?

A bio-based industry is a sector of the economy that uses living organisms or their derivatives to produce various goods and services. This can include industries that produce food, beverages, chemicals, fuels, and other products. Reusing CO₂ in the bio industry has the potential to provide numerous environmental, economic, and social benefits, making it an important area for continued research and development.

What is a catalytic process?

A catalytic process is a chemical reaction that is facilitated or accelerated by a substance called a catalyst. A catalyst works by lowering the activation energy required for a reaction to occur, allowing it to proceed at a faster rate or under milder conditions than would be possible without the catalyst. In other words, it is a chemical reaction that is made faster, more efficient, or more environmentally friendly by the presence of a catalyst.

Do I see those chemicals in my day to day?

- Glyoxylic acid (GA)** is used in the production of pharmaceuticals, dyes, resins, and other chemicals. It is also used as a reducing agent in the synthesis of a variety of organic compounds.
- Lactic acid (LA)** is used in the production of biodegradable plastics, as well as in the food industry as a flavoring agent and preservative. It is also used in the cosmetic and personal care industry as a pH adjuster.
- Furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME)** can be used to produce polymers, resins, and other materials with improved performance and sustainability compared to traditional petroleum-based products.
- Cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters (CCFAMEs)** are used as starting materials for the production of bio-based chemicals and materials, such as surfactants, lubricants, and biodegradable plastics.
- Bio-methanol** is a renewable alternative to petroleum-based methanol. It is used as a fuel, solvent, and starting material for the production of chemicals, such as formaldehyde and acetic acid. Bio-methanol can also be converted into biofuels, such as bio-diesel and bio-jet fuel.

The three projects also agreed to create a joint social media strategy to share the handbook on their respective communication channels (Website, LinkedIn and Twitter) respecting the YES, BUT... approach.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.4.2: Example of social media post about the joint factsheet following the YES, BUT... approach

CATCO₂NVERS
457 followers
Info · Edit · Share

CATCO₂NVERS seeks to transform waste CO₂ from 2 bio-based industries into 5 added-value chemicals.

What is a Bio-Based Industry?

A bio-based industry is a sector of the economy that uses living organisms or their derivatives to produce various goods and services.

Find the top key definitions to understand CATCO₂NVERS in our handbook: The importance of Europe leading the way in Turning CO₂ Emissions into Chemicals: <https://wld.ly/8K2ug1p>

#Catalytic #Biopolymers #electrocatalysis #enzymatic #chemicals

Partners: Wageningen University & Research, CARTE, CSIC, University of Twente, Avantium, PERSEO Biotechnology S.L., Hyytech s.r.l., nova-institut GmbH, DANTEA Sustainable Innovations (SI), alchemia nova AWA, Biochem AG, Evyap Johnson, Matthey, Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM) - CSIC, European Research Executive Agency (REA), European Health and Digital Executive Agency (H4DEA)

**YES, BUT...
What is a Bio-Based Industry?**

A bio-based industry is a sector of the economy that uses living organisms or their derivatives to produce various goods and services. This includes industries that produce food, beverages, chemicals, fuels, and other products. Using CO₂ in the bio industry has the potential to provide business, environmental, economic, and social benefits, making it an important area for continued research and development.

DOWNLOAD OUR HANDBOOK
catco2nvers.eu • 1 min read

Organic impressions: 1,248 impressions Hide stats

Organic stats
Targeted to: All followers

1,248 Impressions	37.02% Engagement rate	433 Clicks
34.7% Click-through rate	23 Reactions	2 Comments
4 Reposts		

Show more analytics

As of September 2023, the handbook has gained more than 1,000 impressions on social media (counting only the analytics of CATCO₂NVERS).

Additionally, SIE organised a joint webinar with the same topic but aiming to reach a scientific target within the research, academia, and industry. On April 12, 2023, the three sister projects organised an [online joint webinar](#) where more than one hundred attendees enjoyed and learnt about the ambition, objectives, impacts, methodologies and concepts of each initiative showcased. The online webinar presented the different technologies and workflows in each project for turning CO₂ into chemicals and it was opened to anyone who wanted to learn more about these initiatives and the different carbon capture methods and conversions.

Image 13.4.3: Joint webinar agenda: The Importance of Europe Leading the Way in Turning CO₂ Emissions into Chemicals.

WEBINAR AGENDA

- 11:00 – 11:10
- 11:10 – 11:30
- 11:30 – 11:40
- 11:40 – 12:00
- 12:00 – 12:20
- 12:20 – 12:30

- 1

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTION
Pablo Morales Moya | SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS
- 2

INTRODUCING CATCO₂NVERS
Dulce Muñoz | FUNDITEC
- 3

BREAK OUT SESSION
Pablo Morales Moya | SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS
- 4

INTRODUCING VIVALDI
Albert Guisasola | UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA DE BARCELONA
- 5

INTRODUCING CO₂SMOS
Raúl Piñero | CARTIF
- 6

WRAP-UP, Q&A
Lara Tottolo | CO₂ VALUE EUROPE
Pablo Morales Moya | SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS

Future conversations will be established to keep defining new communication strategies to maximise impacts and efforts in the upcoming periods.

13.5 Social Media

In the following section, a description of the performance is conducted in terms of the number of followers, number of posts, engagement rate levels as well as graphics and analytics.

13.5.1 LinkedIn

CATCO₂NVERS's presence on LinkedIn has reached 457 followers by M29 after 60 updates. The engagement rate in this platform (number of interactions with post-likes, comments, and shares) has reached 8,85% (more than 2% is considered excellent performance).

The number of impressions (views) from M19 to M29 is around 22500.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.5.1.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn profile. This data does not reflect the October analytics)

Metrics

Impressions ▾

13.5.2 Twitter

As of September 2023, CATCO₂NVERS has 283 followers on this social media channel after 60 updates. The content on the profile has generated more than 10,000 views from M19 to M29. The current engagement rate for Twitter is around 4% (higher than 0,5% is considered great performance).

Image 13.5.2.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M19-M21

Your Tweets earned **2.9K impressions** over this **90 day period**

Image 13.5.2.2: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M22-M24.

Your Tweets earned **3.1K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Image 13.5.2.3: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M25-M27

Your Tweets earned **3.5K impressions** over this **90 day** period

Image 13.5.2.4: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS Twitter profile M28-M29 (Data of this time period is not entirely reflected as of September 11, 2023)

Your Tweets earned **999 impressions** over this **72 day** period

13.5.3 YouTube

To date, CATCO₂NVERS has uploaded six videos reaching more than 350 views in total. SIE has started a proactive campaign with the support of the technical partners involved in the development of the five conversion technologies. This campaign is scheduled to be released in the last quarter of the year. The main objective of this

CATCO₂NVERS

campaign is to explain how the leading technology partners are progressing and conducting their workflows to convert CO₂ into high-value-added chemicals. The campaign is entitled Five Co₂nversion Technologies:

- Technology one: From CO₂ to Lactic Acid.
- Technology two: From CO₂ to Glyoxylic Acid.
- Technology three: From CO₂ to Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester.
- Technology four: From CO₂ to Cyclic Carbonates.
- Technology five: From CO₂ to Bio-Methanol.

Image 12.5.3.1: Five Co₂nversion Technologies intro.

The partners that are collaborating in this video campaign are the leaders of these technologies: Avantium, Wageningen University & Research, CARTIF, and FUNDITEC. Additionally, SIE has collaborated with Nova-Institute to produce one extra video about the importance of Life Cycle Assessment within the CATCO₂NVERS project which is already available on the project YouTube Channel: [About Life Cycle Assessment And Its Importance In The Catco₂nvers Project.](#)

Last but not least, SIE has added subtitles in ten languages in the [CATCO₂NVERS official video](#) to make the video more comprehensive for all kinds of audiences. This video has been translated into the following languages: Catala, Dutch, English, French, German, Portuguese, Spanish, Turkish, and Ukrainian.

13.6 Newsletters

As of M29, the Newsletter has 387 subscribers and an average of 60 readers per Newsletter. The Newsletters are also uploaded to the [Documents section](#) on the CATCO₂NVERS website. From there, users can easily access each Newsletter and subscribe to receive upcoming ones.

Image 13.6.1: Documents Section: CATCO₂NVERS Newsletters

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 13.6.1: Newsletter 4 (left side) Newsletter 5 (right side).

NEWSLETTER 4 | MARCH 2023

FREE ONLINE WEBINAR

LEADING THE WAY IN TURNING CO₂ EMISSIONS INTO CHEMICALS

The fight against **climate change** is an ongoing battle, and one of the biggest contributors to this problem is the **emission of CO₂** into the atmosphere. While CO₂ is a naturally occurring gas, the increase in human activities has led to a sharp rise in CO₂ levels, which is having a devastating effect on our planet. Thankfully, there are forward-thinking European projects that are **leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals**: CATCO₂NVERS, CO₂SMOS, and VIVALDI are innovative projects that are using cutting-edge technology to capture CO₂ emissions and turn them into **valuable chemicals**.

[REGISTER FOR FREE NOW](#)

CATCO₂NVERS HOLD ITS FIRST

REVIEW MEETING WITH THE RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY

On January 18, 2023, the CATCO₂NVERS consortium held the **Review Meeting with the Research Executive Agency** funded by CMC (Spanish National Research Council) in Brussels.

The meeting was an opportunity to provide an introduction and overview of the CATCO₂NVERS project and its different work packages.

The **Research Executive Agency** followed up on the progress made by the CATCO₂NVERS project team and praised their efforts to address the challenges faced. The European Commission agency also provided valuable **feedback and suggestions** for future developments, which are being taken into consideration.

NEWSLETTER 5 | SEPTEMBER 2023

THE PROGRESS AFTER TWO YEARS OF RUNNING

On May 8th and 9th 2023, the partners of the CATCO₂NVERS project had the opportunity to meet and discuss the latest progress of this initiative that is seeking to create added-value chemicals by using the CO₂ of two bio-based industries. The meeting was organised by CARTIF in Valladolid, Spain.

On the first day, the consortium showcased the progress and some results of the technical work packages as well as the current status in the dissemination, communication and exploitation side.

On the second day, the meeting continued with a discussion of the upcoming milestones and deliverables for the project, with the partners agreeing on a clear plan of action for the next few months.

Finally, the consortium enjoyed a tour through the CARTIF facilities where they learned how they are working in the conversion of CO₂ to Bio-Methanol.

[READ MORE](#)

CLUSTERING WITH OUR SISTER PROJECTS

JOINT WORKSHOP WITH CO₂SMOS AND VIVALDI PROJECTS

On April 12, 2023, the three sister projects organised an online joint webinar in the framework of **Leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals** where more than one hundred of attendees enjoyed and learnt about the ambition, objectives, impacts, methodologies and concepts of each initiative showcased.

[WATCH RECORDING](#)

JOINT HANDBOOK

THE IMPORTANCE OF EUROPE

LEADING THE WAY IN TURNING CO₂ EMISSIONS INTO CHEMICALS

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13.7 Website

As a living platform, the website has evolved from M19 to M29 to include all the relevant actions, news, articles and relevant documents developed within the CATCO₂NVERS framework.

Regarding the News section, in the last year twenty blog posts have been published:

- [INTERVIEW WITH TOM EWING – WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH](#)
- [UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE SHOWCASES THE CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT IN SEVERAL EVENTS AND CONFERENCES](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS ATTENDS THE SECAT 2023 IN SPAIN](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS SHOWCASED DURING THE UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE OPEN HOUSE 2023](#)
- [THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL AND CATCO₂NVERS](#)
- [EUROPE DAY: COMMEMORATING THE HISTORIC SCHUMAN DECLARATION](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE ADDING VALUE TO CO₂ CONFERENCE](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS, THE PROGRESS AFTER TWO YEARS OF RUNNING](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH PABLO MORALES, COMMUNICATIONS MANAGER AT SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS PRESENTED AT THE CONFERENCE ON CO₂-BASED FUELS & CHEMICALS 2023](#)
- [LEADING THE WAY IN TURNING CO₂ EMISSIONS INTO CHEMICALS, THE RELATED PROJECTS WEBINAR ORGANISED BY CATCO₂NVERS, VIVALDI AND CO₂SMOS](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS PRESENTED DURING A STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE ON THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH MARCOS LATORRE, PERSEO](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE VIII INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR OF BIOPLASTICS AND SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH OSCAR RAMIREZ, PROJECT COORDINATOR.](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AND ITS FIRST REVIEW MEETING WITH THE RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE NVBMB FALL MEETING](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE PARTICIPATES AT THE 18TH AACHENER MEMBRAN KOLLOQUIUM](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH DULCE MUÑOZ, TECHNICAL COORDINATOR](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS HOLDS ITS SECOND GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN ISTANBUL](#)

Likewise, during this period the following documents have been uploaded to the CATCO₂NVERS website:

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- [Newsletter 4](#)
- Newsletter 5 (as of September 11, 2023 this campaign has not been sent yet)
- [Joint Handbook: of Leading the way in turning CO₂ emissions into chemicals](#)
- [Scientific Paper: Metal-free catalytic systems based on imidazolium chloride](#)

From M19 to M29 the CATCO₂NVERS website has gained around 2400 sessions with an average session duration of 02:94 minutes which means that the audience is very engaged with the content of the website.

Image 13.7.1: Website performance, Audience overview.

In the next image, detailed audience information is displayed where SIE can track relevant information such as the top three pages visited, language breakdown, country breakdown as well as the top devices used:

Image 13.7.2: Website performance, breakdowns.

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13.8 Partners contribution

Apart from the activities listed previously in terms of conferences attended, events organised, campaign participation, and scientific publications, CATCO2NVERS partners have been also active on social media. LinkedIn posts have been shared from M19-M30 and the partners were very supportive in this area. Likewise, consortium members have also made different posts during M19-M30 about CATCO2NVERS plus reported the social media post from CATCO2NVERS social media channels.

Some partners have accounts on other media channels and they have disseminated the project as well over there. The full partner's contribution is listed in the dissemination tables (Annex 1).

14 Actions M31-M54

This section corresponds to the update of the Communication & Dissemination Plan D7.2 (M6) led by SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE). Throughout this section, a complete description of the activities carried out during the month 31 (M31) to month 54 (M54) period in terms of Communication and Dissemination will be further explained.

Likewise, the Communication and Dissemination strategy for the upcoming period will be included. All partners contributed to dissemination and communication activities in line with the aims and goals of the plan.

14.1 Project identity and materials

During the period reported (M31-M54) the partners have distributed several communication materials produced by SIE at the beginning of the project such as the roll-up and brochures.

On November 15th, 2023, the CATCO₂NVERS project participated in the Circular Economy Summit celebrated in Austria through a poster presentation where our partner Alchemia-Nova showcased the project methodology, concept, objectives and impacts.

Image 14.1.1: CATCO₂NVERS poster at the Circular Economy Summit

CATCO₂NVERS

During June and July 2024, JM disseminated several CATCO₂NVERS scientific posters at several trade fairs. In June, Silvia Fruncillo, researcher in biocatalysis at JM, presented a poster during the JM Science Conference on the biocatalytic conversion of CO₂ and bioethanol into L-lactic acid while in July, Silvia presented the same poster at the Biocatalysis GRC.

Image 14.1.2: CATCO₂NVERS poster used in the JM Science Conference and the GRC Conference

On June 13th and 14th, 2024 our coordinator entity FUNDITEC showcased the CATCO₂NVERS project during the MEETECH Spain 2024. The event was organised by Fedit (Spanish Federation of Technological Centers). There, our coordinators had the opportunity to network with collaborators and colleagues from the industry and distributed several copies of the CATCO₂NVERS brochure.

CATCO2NVERS

Image 14.1.3: FUNDiTEC stand at the MEETECH SPAIN 2024.

On October 31st, 2024, as part of CARTIF's 30th-anniversary celebrations, the CATCO2NVERS project was presented to a diverse audience during a special open day where several materials, such as the project roll-up up were distributed.

Image 14.1.4: CARTIF's 30th-anniversary open day to young people.

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From June 29th to July 3rd, 2025, CATCO2NVERS was showcased at the 17th International Symposium on Biocatalysis and Biotransformations (Biotrans 2025), held in Basel, Switzerland. CATCO2NVERS was presented through a scientific poster titled “Enantioselective synthesis of D-lactic acid from CO₂ using a novel pyruvate decarboxylase in a scalable biocatalytic cascade”

Image 14.1.5: Poster presented at the Biotrans 2025

Furthermore, all the materials were updated to include the new partners such as NOVAMONT and LEDA POLYMER. SIE encouraged the new partners to disseminate those materials.

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Image 14.1.6: Partners logos updated with the NOVAMONT and LEDA POLYMER logo included

 This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 953073.

Last but not least, CSIC developed a customized key ring with the CATCO₂NVERS logo for the project final event:

Image 14.1.7: CATCO₂NVERS key ring for the final event.

14.2 Conferences attended

In the current period, the partners attended more than ten conferences and events to disseminate the CATCO2NVERS project. Most of the events listed below have been properly disseminated on the project website as well as social media (hyperlinks are included):

- [XL Biennial Meeting of the Spanish Royal Society of Chemistry](#). July 2025, CSIC. Oral presentation.
- [5th International Symposium on Porous Organic Polymers \(POPs 2025\)](#). August 2025, CSIC. Keynote Lecture.
- [17th International Symposium on Biocatalysis and Biotransformations \(Biotrans 2025\)](#). June 2025, WUR. Poster Presentation
- [CO2SMOS Final Conference](#). April 2025. FUNDITEC. Oral Presentation.
- [Fissati per la CO₂ Conference](#). February 2025. HYSYTECH. Keynote presentation.
- [Chemical Industries Association \(CIA\) Sustainability Conference](#). September 2024. JM. Keynote presentation.
- [XVII Meeting of the Specialized Group on Polymers \(GEP\)](#). September 2024. CSIC. Plenary Talk.
- [Biocatalysis GRC Conference](#). July 2024. JM. Poster Presentation.
- [18th International Congress on Catalysis](#). July 2024. CSIC. Plenary Talk.
- [JM Science Conference](#). July 2024. JM. Poster Presentation.
- [MEETECH Spain 2024](#). June 2024. FUNDITEC. Trade Fair and networking.
- [Circular Economy Summit](#). November 2023. Alchemia Nova. Poster Presentation.

All the events, conferences, and trade fairs were properly disseminated through the different CATCO2NVERS communication channels, such as the website and social media.

The CATCO2NVERS project has been actively disseminated at a wide range of conferences, ensuring visibility across both scientific and industrial audiences. Participation in these events has provided a platform to present the project's objectives, progress, and results, while creating opportunities for dialogue with stakeholders from academia, policy, and business sectors. By engaging with diverse forums, the consortium has positioned the project within broader discussions on sustainable innovation and CO₂ utilisation.

CATCO₂NVERS

To maximise outreach, the project has adopted a variety of formats tailored to each event. These include oral presentations, where project representatives have delivered in-depth insights on specific technical and exploitation aspects; poster sessions, offering accessible summaries of research outcomes; and interactive discussions, which have encouraged direct feedback from participants. Such a multi-format approach has enabled the project to reach both technical specialists and non-specialist audiences, ensuring inclusiveness in its communication strategy.

Through this consistent presence, CATCO₂NVERS has strengthened its visibility and contributed to raising awareness of innovative CO₂ valorisation pathways. The project's engagement in conferences has not only expanded its dissemination impact but also fostered new connections with potential collaborators, end-users, and policymakers. This has reinforced its role as a reference initiative in the field, while paving the way for future exploitation and replication of its results.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 14.2: Example of website event creativities:

14.3 Events organised

As M54, the project has organised several webinars and events to present the different outcomes and results achieved during the project's lifetime.

On October 1st 2025, the final event of the project was organised under the theme "From Emissions to Solutions: The CATCO₂NVERS Journey". During the event, the most impactful results, technological breakthroughs, and collaborative milestones were presented, together with the five conversion technologies developed to transform CO₂ into value-added chemicals. The programme opened with an institutional introduction from a representative of the European Commission Agency, followed by an overview of the project's journey and its final results, milestones, and conclusions. Presentations were then delivered by different consortium partners, highlighting the biorefinery approach and the transformation of CO₂ into glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furandicarboxylic acid methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters, and bio-methanol. The agenda also included a dedicated session on end-user applications, providing insights into the potential market uptake and industrial relevance of the technologies. After a coffee break, the event continued with further technical interventions, a Q&A session, and a structured stakeholder discussion, which created space for dialogue on replication opportunities and policy implications. The day concluded with an interactive session that encouraged feedback from participants, a wrap-up session, and a networking lunch, consolidating the outcomes of nearly five years of collaborative work among partners, industry representatives, policymakers, researchers, and civil society.

Image 14.3.1: Streaming of the event

CATCO₂NVERS

The final event gathered a total of 50 registered participants, 30 physical attendees and 20 virtual attendees, with a strong presence from industry and academia, complemented by participants from policymaking bodies, research organisations, and civil society. This hybrid format ensured broad representation and a balanced exchange of perspectives, highlighting both the scientific and practical dimensions of the project's outcomes and reinforcing the potential for market uptake, replication, and policy relevance.

Image 14.3.2: Images of the CATCO₂NVERS Final Event

From Emissions to Solutions The CATCO₂NVERS Journey

Final Results, Milestones and Conclusions of the CATCO₂NVERS project

AGENDA October 1, 2025 | 09:30 - 15:00 (CET)

National Historical Archive (CSIC): Street Serrano 115, Madrid, Spain.

TIME	TITLE
09:30 - 09:40	The Role of the Research Executive Agency Michael Schäffer, Project Advisor at REA (European Commission Agency)
09:40 - 09:45	Upcoming policies impacting R&I Silvia Maltagliati, Policy Officer
09:45 - 09:50	Introducing the CATCO₂NVERS project Dulce Muñoz, FUNDITEC
09:50 - 10:05	The Biorefinery approach Marcos Latorre, PERSEO Biotechnology
10:05 - 10:20	From CO₂ to Glyoxylic Acid Mariana Paredinha, AVANTIUM
10:20 - 10:35	From CO₂ to Lactic Acid Daan van Vliet, Wageningen University
10:35 - 10:55	Coffee Break
10:55 - 11:10	From CO₂ to Furandicarboxylic Acid Methyl Ester Eva Maya, CSIC
11:10 - 11:25	From CO₂ to Cyclic Carbonated Fatty Acid Methyl Esters Dulce Muñoz, FUNDITEC
11:25 - 11:40	From CO₂ to Bio-Methanol David Díez, CARTIF
11:40 - 12:00	End User Applications Aslı Özge AVCI TUNA, EVYAP & Patrizio Salice NOVAMONT.
12:00 - 12:15	Q&A
12:15 - 13:00	Stakeholder Discussion
13:00 - 13:30	Interactive Session
13:30 - 13:45	Wrap Up
13:45 - 15:00	Lunch

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CATCO₂NVERS

Additionally, on October 31st, 2024, as part of CARTIF's 30th anniversary celebrations, the CATCO₂NVERS project was presented to a diverse audience during a special open day. The contribution of CARTIF within the project focused on converting CO₂ into biomethanol as a sustainable alternative fuel, which was highlighted as a key solution to address pressing environmental challenges. As a key partner, CARTIF showcased its pioneering role in developing the technology behind this transformation. The presentation, delivered by project researchers, engaged the general public and emphasised the significance of scientific advancements in tackling climate change. The explanations made the complex processes of CO₂ conversion accessible to attendees of all ages and underlined the project's contribution to advancing a circular carbon economy.

Image 14.3.3: CARTIF's 30th anniversary Open Day

The open day also provided an opportunity for participants to connect with CARTIF's broader mission of innovation and sustainability. By highlighting the project, the event reinforced the centre's commitment to fostering solutions that combine scientific excellence with societal benefits, while inspiring future generations to engage with cutting-edge research.

On April 11th, 2024, an online webinar entitled “From CO₂ to Chemicals: Five Conversion Technologies” was organised to disseminate knowledge and foster collaboration. Jointly coordinated by seven project partners, the webinar showcased the latest advancements and discoveries in the field of CO₂ conversion into valuable chemicals. It was open to all interested participants and attracted a wide audience from different stakeholder groups.

The session presented the context of climate change and the critical role of CO₂ emissions, underlining the urgent need for innovative solutions. The project's approach to mitigating greenhouse gas emissions from bio-based industries was explained, with a focus on converting waste CO₂ into five high-value chemicals: glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, furan dicarboxylic methyl ester, cyclic carbonated fatty acid methyl esters, and bio-methanol. The potential applications of these chemicals across various sectors were emphasised, highlighting their relevance as sustainable alternatives to fossil-based materials.

The webinar also provided insights into carbon capture methods and their pivotal role in addressing climate change by reducing emissions and supporting the development of eco-friendly products. By facilitating interaction and exchange between participants, the event contributed to raising awareness of innovative CO₂ valorisation pathways and promoting collaboration for future developments.

Image 14.3.4: Recording of the Webinar From CO₂ to Chemicals: Five Conversion Technologies.

The screenshot displays a webinar interface with the following elements:

- Logo:** CATCO₂NVERS
- Title:** WEBINAR AGENDA AND NOTICES
- Agenda Table:**

TIME	TITLE
11:00 - 11:05	Welcome and Introduction Pablo Morales Moya, Sustainable Innovations
11:05 - 11:15	End users' perspective Robert Dettmer on behalf of Eynco
11:15 - 11:25	Tech 1: From CO ₂ to Glyoxylic Acid Marlene Krings, Aachen
11:25 - 11:35	Tech 2: From CO ₂ to Lactic Acid Tom Ewing, Wageningen University & Research
11:35 - 11:40	Mentimeter Activity Pablo Morales Moya, Sustainable Innovations
11:40 - 11:50	Tech 3: From CO ₂ to Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester Eva Moya, CIRC
11:50 - 12:00	Tech 4: From CO ₂ to Cyclic Carbonated Fatty Acid Methyl Esters Dario Malini, Aachen
12:00 - 12:10	Tech 5: From CO ₂ to Bioethanol María Antón, CIATEP
12:10 - 12:15	Q&A
- Online Webinar Section:** FROM CO₂ TO CHEMICALS: FIVE CONVERSION TECHNOLOGIES. Includes a row of seven speaker profile pictures.
- Interactive Elements:**
 - Microphone icon: "Please, make sure your microphone is muted"
 - Chat icon: "Use the chat function to enter your questions"
 - Mobile icon: "This is an interactive session, please, participate on menti.com"
- Recording Status:** "This session is being recorded"
- Video Player:** Shows a progress bar at 0:05 / 1:18:07.
- Participant Video:** A small video window in the top right corner shows a participant named PABLO MORALES - 5.

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In total, the webinar gathered 55 unique participants after removing duplicate registrations. The audience reflected a balanced representation of stakeholders, with 47.3% from industry and 38.2% from academia, together accounting for the majority of attendees. In addition, 12.7% of participants represented other organisations, while 1.8% came from civil society. This distribution demonstrated the strong engagement of both research and industrial communities, complemented by broader societal actors, ensuring diverse perspectives in the discussions on CO₂ conversion technologies.

14.4 Interaction with EU projects

The collaboration with CO₂SMOS and VIVALDI remained solid and proactive. On February 20th, 2024, the three sister projects CATCO₂NVERS, VIVALDI AND CO₂SMOS organized a joint webinar titled “Addressing Challenges and Unlocking Carbon Capture Utilisation: Circular Carbon Advancement through Policy Reform”. The main objective was to bring attention to the hurdles and barriers identified across three projects for EU policymakers and regulators. The central focus was on discussing potential solutions, specifically emphasizing the incentives required to promote the integration of alternative carbon feedstock in essential products, such as through the implementation of quotas under EU legislation. The workshop delved into various carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) pathways aimed at de-fossilizing chemical production, examined ongoing EU-level discussions in this domain, and provided recommendations to shift away from fossil resources in the manufacturing of chemicals and products.

Image 13.4.1: Recording of the webinar *Addressing Challenges and Unlocking Carbon Capture Utilisation*.

Policy workshop “Addressing Challenges and Unlocking Carbon Capture Utilization”

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Last but not least, on April 1st 2025, the CATCO₂NVERS project actively participated in the CO₂SMOS Final Conference, a key event that brought together European experts to discuss the future of CO₂-based technologies in advancing a circular and sustainable economy. The event featured a rich programme of presentations and discussions on cutting-edge carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) innovations.

Image 13.4.1: CATCO₂NVERS at the CO₂SMOS Final Conference

Dulce Muñoz, the project coordinator of CATCO₂NVERS, presented an update on the project's current status, highlighting significant milestones achieved so far. Her presentation underlined CATCO₂NVERS' complementary role alongside CO₂SMOS and VIVALDI, showcasing how collaborative research is propelling CCU technologies forward across the continent.

14.5 Social Media

In the following section, a description of the performance is conducted in terms of the number of followers, number of posts, engagement rate levels as well as graphics and analytics.

14.5.1 LinkedIn

CATCO₂NVERS's presence on LinkedIn has reached 774 followers by M54. Weekly updates were put in place. The engagement rate in this platform (number of

interactions with post-likes, comments, and shares) has reached more than 5% (more than 2% is considered excellent performance).

The number of impressions (views) during the last year remains higher than 20,000, which indicates a good performance.

Image 14.5.1.1: Number of Impressions for CATCO₂NVERS LinkedIn profile. This data does not reflect the October analytics)

14.5.2 Twitter

As of September 2025, CATCO₂NVERS has 352 followers on this social media channel after weekly updates.

Analytics from Twitter (now X) are not included in this report, as the platform no longer provides free access to performance data. Following recent changes, detailed analytics have been placed behind a paid subscription model, which limits the availability of these insights without additional costs.

14.5.3 YouTube

To date, CATCO₂NVERS has uploaded eight videos reaching more than 1200 views in total. SIE continued the campaign to explain [the five conversion technologies](#). The following videos were published and disseminated through Social Media Channels:

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- [Technology three: From CO₂ to Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester.](#)
- [Technology four: From CO₂ to Cyclic Carbonates.](#)
- [Technology five: From CO₂ to Bio-Methanol.](#)

Image 14.5.3.1: Five Co₂nversion Technologies Playlist

During the period M31–M54, the recording, editing, and dissemination of [the final CATCO₂NVERS video](#) were carried out. The video served as a comprehensive overview of the project, explaining its overall objectives and the milestones achieved. It presented the project's mission to reduce CO₂ emissions from bio-industries while developing innovative catalytic technologies to transform these emissions into valuable bioproducts. The narrative highlighted the role of biorefineries in supplying biogenic CO₂, the validation of the technologies under different purity conditions, and the broader contribution to a circular and sustainable carbon economy.

Image 14.5.3.2: Final Project Video Frames

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The video also detailed the three catalytic routes developed within the project: electrochemical, enzymatic, and thermocatalytic, each leading to the production of key chemicals such as glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, FDME, cyclic carbonates, and bio-methanol. Attention was given to downstream processes aimed at achieving high-purity products suitable for industrial use, as well as to the formulation of some of these compounds in cosmetics and personal care applications. The dissemination concluded with an emphasis on the project's relevance for industry replication and public engagement, supported by references to its social media channels and website.

Last but not least, SIE also uploaded two capacity-building trainings that are part of the [Training Section](#).

Image 14.5.3.3: Final Project Video Frames

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These videos contain insights into the global landscape for CO₂ conversion technologies, and they are part of the capacity building programme that seeks to highlight the potential for carbon conversion technologies to enhance the replicability of bio-based industries and create new opportunities in a variety of sectors.

14.5.4 Zenodo

Zenodo is an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE programme and operated by CERN, designed to ensure long-term preservation and visibility of research outputs. For CATCO₂NVERS, SIE established this platform since it was considered a key dissemination channel, fully aligned with the European Commission's commitment to Open Science and the FAIR principles of making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. By using Zenodo, the project guarantees that its scientific papers, datasets, and supporting materials are permanently accessible and citable through the assignment of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), thus ensuring transparency and traceability of results.

The [CATCO₂NVERS community on Zenodo](#) hosts a comprehensive collection of fourteen scientific and dissemination outputs that reflect the project's advances in CO₂ valorisation. The materials include several datasets accompanying journal articles that report on innovative catalytic processes, such as the selective electro-oxidation of ethylene glycol, the development of hypercrosslinked porous polymers, and the design of metal-free catalytic systems for the oxidative esterification of furfural, as well as the synthesis of formamides from amines using CO₂. Other contributions focus on the formation of bio-based cyclic carbonates and the insertion of CO₂ into 2-methyl furoate for the production of monomers of CO₂-based biopolymers. Together, these research datasets make the experimental data, characterisation results, and performance evaluations openly accessible, ensuring reproducibility and transparency. In addition, the repository includes project deliverables such as the Market Assessment Questionnaire Results, which explores customer segments, competitors, and trends related to Key Exploitable Results, and the official reports D6.1 – Report on LCA and LCC: Screening test and first recommendations and D7.2 – Communication and Dissemination Plan M1–M30. By making these resources publicly available with permanent DOIs, the project reinforces its commitment to Open Science and maximises the impact of its scientific and exploitation results across academia, industry, and policy-making stakeholders. Moreover, further contributions are expected to be uploaded, as subsequent results and outputs may arise beyond the current collection, ensuring the repository continues to grow as a reference source for the project's legacy.

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Image 14.5.1: Zenodo Repository

The screenshot displays a grid of research data items from the Zenodo repository. Each item includes a date, a title, a brief description, and a download icon. The items are as follows:

- May 27, 2024 (v1)**: Elemental trade-off in the selective Electrooxidation of Ethylene Glycol on Palladium-Silver/Nickel Electrodes. Authors: Watson, Noé Inna, van den Bosch, Bart, Rotherberg, Gadi, and 2 others. Description: We study the synthesis and properties of PdAg electrodes coated on Ni foam and their application in the selective electro-oxidation of ethylene glycol to glycolate. This reaction is a route to glycolic acid, which is a key component of biodegradable packaging. Using a combination of cyclic voltammetry, EDX and XRD analysis, we find that a 3:1 PdAg ratio gives optimal results. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on May 27, 2024 (Published in: ChemSusChem, 2024). 7 downloads.
- December 4, 2024 (v1)**: Research Data for the Journal Article: Formation of bio-based cyclic carbonates from CO2 and renewable feedstocks via porous poly(azomethine)-based heterogeneous catalysts approach. Authors: Echavarrán Muñoz, Marcelo A., Maya, Eva María, Muñoz, Dulce. Description: The document discusses the synthesis of bio-based cyclic carbonates from CO2 and renewable feedstocks using a porous poly(azomethine)-based heterogeneous catalyst. It includes experimental data such as NMR and FTIR spectra, the performance of catalysts like Fe-PAM-2, and the physical properties of poly(azomethine) supports. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on December 5, 2024. 24 downloads.
- November 29, 2024 (v1)**: Formation of bio-based cyclic carbonates from CO2 and renewable feedstocks via porous poly(azomethine)-based heterogeneous catalysts approach. Authors: Echavarrán Muñoz, Marcelo A., Maya, Eva María, Muñoz, Dulce. Description: Thermocatalytic conversion of CO2 to bio-based cyclic carbonates. Heterogeneous porous catalysts with high efficiency and recovery. Mild condition's reaction: 7 bar of CO2, 120°C and 18 h. Improved catalytic performance compared to reference catalytic systems. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on December 5, 2024 (Published in: Journal of CO2 Utilization, 90, ISSN: 2212-8820, 2024). 13 downloads.
- October 28, 2024 (v1)**: CATCO2NVERS Market Assessment Questionnaire Results. Author: Añillo, Pablo. Description: This dataset contains the results of a market assessment questionnaire conducted as part of the CATCO2NVERS project, focused on exploring the potential markets, competitors, customer segments, and state-of-the-art trends for the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project. The survey was completed by various project partners and provides valuable insights into... Part of EU Open Research Resources. Updated on October 29, 2024. 47 downloads.
- October 25, 2024 (v1)**: Research Data for the Journal Article: Insertion of CO2 to 2-methyl furate promoted by a cobalt hypercrosslinked polymer catalyst to obtain a monomer of CO2-based biopolyesters. Authors: Rangel-Rangel, Elizabeth, Fuente-Díaz, Beatriz, Iglesias, Marta, and 1 other. Description: No description. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on October 25, 2024. 71 downloads.
- October 25, 2024 (v1)**: Research Data for the Journal Article: Hypercrosslinked porous polymer as catalyst for efficient biodiesel production. Authors: Salazar, Sara, Rangel-Rangel, Elizabeth, Maya, Eva María, and 1 other. Description: No description. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on October 25, 2024. 72 downloads.
- October 25, 2024 (v1)**: Research Data for the Journal Article: Efficient DMF-assisted synthesis of formamides from amines using CO2 catalyzed by heterogeneous metal-free imidazolium-hypercrosslinked polymers. Authors: Fuente-Díaz, Beatriz, Rangel-Rangel, Elizabeth, Iglesias, Marta, and 1 other. Description: No description. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on October 25, 2024. 45 downloads.
- October 24, 2024 (v1)**: Research Data for the Journal Article: Metal-free catalytic systems based on imidazolium chloride and strong bases for selective oxidative esterification of furfural to methyl furate. Authors: Cuello, Nathalia Marcela, de Beuk, Nees. Description: No description. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on October 24, 2024. 20 downloads.
- May 24, 2024 (v1)**: DB.1 - Report on LCA and LCC: Screening test and first recommendations. Authors: Cuello, Nathalia Marcela, de Beuk, Nees. Description: No description. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on October 17, 2024. 13 downloads.
- September 13, 2024 (v1)**: Insertion of CO2 to 2-methyl furate promoted by a cobalt hypercrosslinked polymer catalyst to obtain a monomer of CO2-based biopolyesters. Authors: Eva M. Maya, Elizabeth Rangel-Rangel, Beatriz Fuente-Díaz, and 1 other. Description: 2,5-Furan Dicarboxylic Methyl Ester (FDME), a highly valued monomer for the synthesis of bio-based polyesters, has been prepared through a new synthetic strategy that consists of the direct carboxylation of methyl furate in two steps: the first one involves a solvent-free reaction using a moderate CO2 pressure (10 bar), a base (CaCO3) and a cobalt-based heterogeneous catalyst... Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on October 3, 2024. 15 downloads.
- June 2024 (v1)**: Hypercrosslinked porous polymer as catalyst for efficient biodiesel production. Author: Eva M. Maya. Description: While porous organic polymers (POPs) are known for their unique properties, their application in basic biodiesel catalysis is innovative. This study introduces a novel catalyst: hypercrosslinked polymer (HCP-SB-A), synthesized through mechanochemical polymerization of styrene and benzaldehyde with a cross-linking agent and FeCl3, followed by calcination of the previous polymer. Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on August 9, 2024 (Published in: Reactive and Functional Polymers, 2024). 14 downloads.
- August 5, 2024 (v1)**: Efficient DMF-assisted synthesis of formamides from amines using CO2 catalyzed by heterogeneous metal-free imidazolium-hypercrosslinked polymers. Author: Eva M. Maya. Description: CO2 emissions are constantly increasing, so it is necessary to continue working to mitigate the excess of CO2 in the atmosphere and reduce the effects it has on the environment. In this regard, we have developed novel catalysts by synthesizing ionic liquids based on imidazolium chloride, supported on hyper-crosslinked polymers (HCP-domainD and HCP-Epo(EpoMmC)). These... Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on August 9, 2024 (Published in: Journal of CO2 Utilization, ISSN: 2212-8820, 2024). 12 downloads.
- March 25, 2024 (v1)**: Metal-free catalytic systems based on imidazolium chloride and strong bases for selective oxidative esterification of furfural to methyl furate. Authors: Homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic systems based on 1-benzyl-3-imidazolium chloride (BenzimC) assisted by strong bases (CaCO3 or 1, 8-diazabicyclo [5.4.0] undec-7-ene (DBU)) were applied in the catalytic esterification of furfural, to obtain 2-methyl-furate (MF). The reaction was carried out in one step, using oxygen as a unique source of oxidation and... Part of CATCO2NVERS H2020. Updated on August 5, 2024 (Published in: Applied Catalysis A, General, ISSN: 0926-8601, 2023). 17 downloads.
- July 4, 2024 (v1)**: D7.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan M1-M30. Authors: Sustainable Innovations Europe, Spanish MDR. Description: This document corresponds to D7.2 and describes the Communication and Dissemination Plan (contract no. 101000580) to be adopted by the CATCO2NVERS project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, models and simulation tools, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to the appropriate target... Part of EU Open Research Resources. Updated on July 8, 2024. 13 downloads.

14.6 Newsletters

As of M54, the Newsletter has 428 subscribers and an average of 60 readers per Newsletter. From M31 to M54, four newsletters were sent containing the relevant information about the project.

- **Newsletter 6 | MARCH 2024:** Newsletter 6 featured the announcement of the free online webinar “From CO₂ to Chemicals: Five Conversion Technologies”, together with highlights from the joint clustering webinar with sister projects addressing policy barriers to carbon capture utilisation. It also presented the project's contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals, introduced new videos on CO₂ conversion, and reported on participation in the Circular Economy Summit in Austria. In addition, it shared interviews with project partners about their roles and challenges, disseminated recent scientific publications on catalytic systems and CO₂-based reactions, and provided an overview of the consortium's general assembly meeting at Wageningen University, which reviewed progress and milestones from the previous six months.

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- Newsletter 7 | SEPTEMBER 2024: Newsletter 7, published in September 2024, reported on the second review meeting of the CATCO₂NVERS project, held with the Research Executive Agency in Amsterdam, where the consortium showcased progress across all conversion technologies and received constructive feedback to guide the final project year. It also highlighted media coverage, with an article in the Innovation News Network explaining the project's main objectives and technologies, and shared the recording of the joint clustering webinar with sister projects focused on carbon capture and utilisation policy challenges. Updates on conferences and events included presentations at the Biocatalysis GRC Conference, the International Congress on Catalysis, the JM Science Conference, and MEETECH Spain 2024, where project results and new catalysts drew considerable interest. The newsletter further featured a partner interview on the importance of exploitation strategies, reported on the consortium meeting hosted by PERSEO Biotechnology in Valencia to advance technical developments, and disseminated the latest scientific publication on hypercrosslinked porous polymers as catalysts for biodiesel production.
- Newsletter 8 | MARCH 2025: Newsletter 8, published in March 2025, reported on the last general assembly meeting of the CATCO₂NVERS consortium, held in Turin and hosted by HYSYTECH, where partners discussed the latest technical developments and visited the facilities, including the future reactor to be used within the project. The newsletter also launched the new training section, providing resources tailored to businesses and policymakers to support the replicability of carbon conversion technologies across bio-based industries, and announced the release of the project's final video showcasing its five innovative technologies and achievements. Updates on conferences and events included the participation of CSIC at the XVII Meeting of the Specialized Group on Polymers in Spain, contributions to the "Fissati per la #CO₂" conference in Turin, and the presentation of project-related results at the CIA Sustainability Conference in Leeds. It further highlighted the dissemination of the project during CARTIF's 30th anniversary open day, which engaged the public in understanding the potential of CO₂ conversion for sustainable industry, and concluded with references to newly published scientific outputs.
- Newsletter 9 | OCTOBER 2025: The last project Newsletter included information about the final project event as well as the last conferences and events attended by the partners such as the POPs 2025 or the Biennial Meeting of the Spanish Royal Society of Chemistry, among others. Scientific publications were also shared, and other milestones such as the cum laude academic distinction from Beatriz Fuertes (CSIC).

14.7 Website

As a living platform, the website has evolved from M31 to M54 to include all the relevant actions, news, articles, and relevant documents developed within the CATCO₂NVERS framework.

Regarding the News section, in the last months, the following blog posts have been published:

- [CATCO₂NVERS CELEBRATES ITS FINAL EVENT](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT SHOWCASED AT XL BIENNIAL MEETING OF THE SPANISH ROYAL SOCIETY OF CHEMISTRY](#)
- [CSIC RESEARCHER BEATRIZ FUERTES AWARDED CUM LAUDE FOR HER DOCTORAL THESIS IN CATCO₂NVERS](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE 5TH INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON POROUS ORGANIC POLYMERS \(POPs 2025\)](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS FEATURED AT THE 17TH INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON BIOCATALYSIS AND BIOTRANSFORMATIONS \(BIOTRANS 2025\)](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS HOLDS ITS LAST GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEETING](#)
- [THE CATCO₂NVERS PROTOTYPE IS NOW MANUFACTURED AND INSTALLED](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS SHOWCASES PROGRESS AT CO₂SMOS FINAL CONFERENCE](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT SHOWCASED AT "FISSATI PER LA CO₂," CONFERENCE AT POLITECNICO DI TORINO](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT SHOWCASED TO YOUNG AUDIENCE DURING CARTIF'S 30TH ANNIVERSARY OPEN DAY](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS CELEBRATES ITS GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN TURIN, ITALY](#)
- [JOHNSON MATTHEY PRESENTS THE CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT AT THE CIA SUSTAINABILITY CONFERENCE 2024](#)
- [CSIC SHOWCASES CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT AT THE XVII GEP MEETING ON POLYMERS](#)
- [EU GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS DROP 4% IN THE FIRST QUARTER OF 2024](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS SHOWCASED AT THE BIOCATALYSIS GRC CONFERENCE](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS ATTENDS THE 18th INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON CATALYSIS](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS CELEBRATES ITS SECOND REVIEW MEETING](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS SHOWCASED DURING THE JM SCIENCE CONFERENCE](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE MEETECH SPAIN 2024](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS CELEBRATES ITS GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN VALENCIA, SPAIN](#)

- [FROM CO₂ TO CHEMICALS: FIVE CONVERSION TECHNOLOGIES](#)
- [INTERVIEW WITH PABLO ARIÑO – SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS, VIVALDI AND CO₂SMOS TOGETHER IN A JOINT WEBINAR ABOUT CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS RELATED TO CARBON CAPTURE AND UTILISATION](#)
- [THE CATCO₂NVERS PROJECT AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS](#)
- [CATCO₂NVERS AT THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY SUMMIT IN AUSTRIA](#)
- [THE CATCO₂NVERS CONSORTIUM GATHERED IN THE WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY](#)

Likewise, during this period, the following documents have been uploaded to the CATCO₂NVERS website:

- [Newsletter 6 | MARCH 2024](#)
- [Newsletter 7 | SEPTEMBER 2024](#)
- [Newsletter 8 | MARCH 2025](#)
- [Newsletter 9 | OCTOBER 2025](#)
- [x2 Training videos](#)
- [X2 Public Deliverables](#)
- [X2 Scientific Publications](#)
- [X2 Press Releases](#)
- [X6 videos](#)

An important update of the CATCO₂NVERS website was the inclusion of a new section entitled The CATCO₂NVERS Technologies where non-technical content and videos were provided to explain the project's technologies and results in an accessible way for all audiences. The section presented the five CO₂ conversion technologies developed within the project, describing how emissions were transformed into valuable chemicals and materials with applications ranging from cosmetics to bioplastics and green fuels. Each technology was introduced with clear explanations and visual resources, avoiding technical jargon, so that policymakers, industry stakeholders, researchers, and the general public could easily understand the scientific progress and societal relevance of the project. This approach ensured that the project's outcomes were communicated in a transparent, inclusive, and engaging manner, maximising outreach and impact.

CATCO₂NVERS

Image 14.7.1: The CATCO₂NVERS Technology website section.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar with links for ABOUT, DOCUMENTS, TRAINING, NEWS, CONTACT, and PRIVATE AREA, along with a language selection icon (EN). Below this, the main content area features two technology sections:

Technology 1: Electrocatalytic Conversion of CO₂ to Glyoxylic Acid

Avantium has developed an innovative two-step process to convert CO₂ into glyoxylic acid for the cosmetics industry. This method first transforms CO₂ into oxalic acid in a non-aqueous medium, then reduces it to glyoxylic acid in water. Using sustainable, non-toxic electrodes, it avoids lead-based catalysts, improving environmental and operational efficiency. The University of Twente has refined this process to meet the purity standards for cosmetics. The next phase will involve testing the technology in demonstration units to scale the CO₂-to-glyoxylic acid conversion model.

Technology 2: Biocatalytic Conversion of CO₂ to Lactic Acid

Researchers at Wageningen University & Research, alongside Johnson Matthey, have developed a biocatalytic process that converts CO₂ emissions and bio-ethanol from biobased industries into lactic acid, used in cosmetics and biodegradable plastics. Utilizing efficient new enzymes, they demonstrated production from gas mixtures that mimic industrial CO₂ streams. This eco-friendly approach advances enzymatic CO₂ utilization, offering potential in green chemistry applications.

Additionally, the CATCO₂NVERS website included a new system to translate the website into several languages, including English, Spanish, French, Dutch, German, Italian, Portuguese, and Turkish. SIE also communicated the update on the social media platforms, and the translation icon is visible in the top right corner:

Image 14.7.2: Example of the website translation into Spanish

The screenshot shows a social media post from CATCO₂NVERS (774 followers). The post text reads: "We are glad to share with you an important update on our project website! The CATCO₂NVERS web is now available in #eight languages!" Below this, a list of languages is provided: English, Spanish, French, Dutch, German, Italian, Portuguese, and Turkish. A note says "Click on the flag icon and select your language!" with the URL <https://catco2nvers.eu/>. The post also includes a list of consortium members: #Catalytic #biopolymers #electrocatalysis #enzymatic #chemicals Funditec Wageningen University & Research CARTIF CSIC University of Twente Avantium PERSEO Biotechnology S.L. Hysytech s.r.l. nova-Institut GmbH DAN'NA Sustainable Innovations (SIE) Eyvap Johnson Matthey Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM - CSIC) Novamont Leda Polymer.

The screenshot shows the website in Spanish. The header includes the logo and navigation links: ACERCA DE, DOCUMENTOS, CAPACITACIÓN, NOTICIAS, CONTACTO, and ÁREA PRIVADA. A language selection menu is visible on the right, with Spanish (ES) selected. The main content area features a banner for "LAS TECNOLOGÍAS CATCO₂NVERS" with the subtitle "Descubre las cinco tecnologías de conversión para transformar el CO₂ en productos químicos valiosos". Below this, the first technology is highlighted: "Tecnología 1: Conversión electrocatalítica de CO₂ en ácido glioxílico". A video thumbnail for this technology is also shown.

CATCO₂NVERS

Regarding website statistics, between November 2023 and September 2025, the CATCO₂NVERS website attracted 3,621 total users, of which 3,570 were new visitors, indicating that almost all the traffic consisted of first-time users. In total, the site registered 5,159 sessions and 9,015 page views, with an engagement rate of just over 50%. Users engaged for a combined 64 hours and 25 minutes, averaging about one minute per visitor. Traffic was largely direct (1,861 users) or referred from Google (735 users), while specialised platforms such as Leadsigo.io, LinkedIn, Bing, and Hysytech provided smaller but notable contributions. Desktop access clearly dominated (75.7%), followed by mobile devices (23.9%) and minimal tablet use.

The audience profile was international, though highly concentrated. The United States accounted for the largest share (32.2%), followed by Spain (18.7%), the Netherlands (7.9%), and Italy (7.5%), with additional presence from France, Germany, and the United Kingdom. In terms of language, English speakers formed the overwhelming majority (68.2%), while Spanish represented 17.2%, and Italian, German, and French collectively contributed smaller but visible shares. The most visited page was the CATCO₂NVERS Value Chain section, attracting over 2,600 users, followed by content explaining the project's concept and methodology, downloadable materials, and the contact page. This pattern shows that visitors primarily sought to understand the project's technological framework and impact, with high engagement in accessing technical resources and keeping up with news updates.

CATCO2NVERS

Image 14.7.3: Website performance, Audience overview.

14.8 Press Releases

During M31-M54, SIE launched two official press releases to disseminate its major milestones and achievements. The first, issued in December 2024, presented the breakthrough development of five novel CO₂ conversion technologies capable of producing value-added chemicals such as glyoxylic acid, lactic acid, FDME, cyclic carbonates, and bio-methanol. This communication highlighted the innovative catalytic, biocatalytic, and thermocatalytic processes developed within the consortium, underscoring their potential for industrial application across sectors from cosmetics to green fuels. The second, released in September 2025, announced the project's Final Event in Madrid, where the consortium showcased the outcomes of nearly five years of work, including technological demonstrations and the validation of its conversion routes in collaboration with industrial partners.

Both press releases were distributed broadly, being sent to approximately 200 media outlets in English and 200 in Spanish. The decision to publish in Spanish reflected the significant representation of Spanish partners within the consortium and ensured that the project's progress reached national stakeholders effectively. As a result, CATCO₂NVERS achieved visibility in specialised and general media, with coverage in outlets such as WIT NEWS, Energética 21, and Revista PQ, among others. This wide dissemination effort contributed to raising awareness of the project's contribution to CO₂ valorisation and its relevance for European climate and innovation goals.

Image 14.8.1: Examples of Media Publications

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14.9 Scientific Publications

Throughout the lifetime of CATCO₂NVERS, six scientific papers were published in peer-reviewed journals, disseminating the technological advances achieved by the consortium. These publications covered a broad spectrum of research topics, including the development of metal-free catalytic systems for the oxidative esterification of furfural to methyl furoate (Applied Catalysis A, General), the synthesis of formamides from amines using CO₂ and hypercrosslinked polymers (Journal of CO₂ Utilization), and the use of hypercrosslinked porous polymers as catalysts for efficient biodiesel production (Reactive and Functional Polymers). Further contributions included the insertion of CO₂ into 2-methyl furoate to produce monomers for CO₂-based biopolyesters (RSC Sustainability), the formation of bio-based cyclic carbonates from renewable feedstocks using porous heterogeneous catalysts (Journal of CO₂ Utilization), and research on the electrooxidation of ethylene glycol on palladium-silver/nickel electrodes (ChemSusChem).

All six papers were published under open access conditions, ensuring that their results are widely available to the scientific and industrial communities. It should be noted that additional publications may follow after the formal conclusion of the project, as the timelines for peer review and journal acceptance often extend beyond the project's end date. SIE has overseen the monitoring of publications, their upload to the project website, and their promotion through social media channels, guaranteeing broad visibility and alignment with open science principles.

In addition, both the current and forthcoming scientific papers can be deposited in the CATCO₂NVERS Zenodo community, ensuring long-term preservation, traceability, and discoverability. By archiving these publications in Zenodo, the project further strengthens its commitment to open science and maximises the accessibility of its results for researchers, industry, policymakers, and society at large.

15. Conclusions

Over the 54 months of implementation, the project has successfully met and in most cases exceeded the majority of the communication and dissemination KPIs initially defined in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (M6). The activities carried out under this Work Package have ensured consistent visibility of the project, effective dissemination of its results, and a strong engagement with stakeholders across different levels. The performance achieved demonstrates the robustness of the strategy put in place and its capacity to adapt to the evolving needs of the consortium and the project lifecycle. The collaboration with project partners has been central to this achievement. Their active involvement in content generation, joint participation in events, and contributions to dissemination channels have been essential to ensuring the effective reach of all planned activities. The continuous flow of information between partners has allowed the consortium to align messages, coordinate timing, and guarantee coherence in the communication of project results.

This cooperative dynamic has provided the necessary framework to go beyond the planned objectives and secure visibility across multiple audiences and platforms. The strategy implemented has been holistic, engaging a broad spectrum of stakeholders. It has ensured the integration of the most academic and industrial actors while also reaching the general public, as has been demonstrated throughout the different sections of this deliverable.

This comprehensive approach has reinforced the relevance of the project and enhanced the uptake of its results in multiple contexts. The outcomes are not limited to the formal conclusion of the project. Dissemination efforts are expected to continue, especially in relation to scientific publications, as the timelines of peer review and acceptance processes often extend beyond the end of funded activities. Future publications resulting from the project's technical work will be disseminated through the same channels established during the project, ensuring continuity and maximising impact. This forward-looking approach guarantees that the communication of CATCO₂NVERS outputs will remain active and relevant even after the official closure of the project.

In summary, the Work Package has been delivered successfully, achieving and surpassing its objectives through a combination of careful planning, strong partner collaboration, and sustained engagement. The lessons learned and the established communication structures provide a solid basis for ensuring that the project's results will continue to generate value and visibility beyond its funded duration.

ANNEX 1: DISSEMINATION TABLES (M31-M54)

TYPE OF ACTIVITY	MAIN LEADER /AUTHORS	TITLE	DATE	PLACE	TOTAL	LINK TO WEBSITE /SOCIAL MEDIA	FLYERS DISTRIBUTED	OPEN ACCESS	BRIEF DESCRIPTION
					NUMBER				
FUNDITEC									
POST	FUNDITEC	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN	nov-24	LINKEDIN	2600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7265745499297628160/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN
REPOST	FUNDITEC	CO2NVERSION TECHNOLOGIES	nov-24	TWITTER	334	https://x.com/Catco2N/status/1856253554635284693	NO	YES	CO2NVERSION TECHNOLOGIES
REPOST	FUNDITEC	CSIC PAPER	dic-24	LINKEDIN	2700	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7275518888593752064/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	CSIC PAPER
POST	FUNDITEC	FUNDITEC PAPER	dic-24	LINKEDIN	2700	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7271903787915575299/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FUNDITEC PAPER
REPOST	FUNDITEC	CSIC SCIENTIFIC PAPER	ene-25	LINKEDIN	2700	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7275518888593752064/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	CSIC SCIENTIFIC PAPER
WEBSITE POST	FUNDITEC	WEBSITE POST ABOUT SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION	ABRIL 2025	WEBSITE	NA	https://funditec.es/es/catco2nvers-nueva-publicacion-cientifica-del-proyecto/	NO	YES	WEBSITE POST ABOUT SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION
POST	FUNDITEC	FINAL EVENT PROMO	sep-25	LINKEDIN	6300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7371581991248494592/?actorCompanyId=76843420	O	YES	FINAL EVENT PROMO
HYSYTECH									
REPOST	HYSYTECH	PRESS RELEASE	NOVEMBER 2023	LINKEDIN	3300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128006242005860352/?actorCompanyId=76843420	YES	NO	PRESS RELEASE
REPOST	HYSYTECH	VIDEO IN 10 LANGUAGES	DECEMBER 2023	LINKEDIN	3360	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7140289331612606466/?actorCompanyId=76843420	YES	NO	VIDEO IN 10 LANGUAGES
REPOST	HYSYTECH	WEBSITE IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES	ene-24	LINKEDIN	3360	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7154099510296616961/?actorCompanyId=76843420	YES	NO	WEBSITE IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES
POST	HYSYTECH	WEBINAR ABOUT CONVERSION TECHNOLOGIES	mar-24	LINKEDIN	3481	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171831475086999553/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	WEBINAR ABOUT CONVERSION TECHNOLOGIES
POST	HYSYTECH	PAPER CSIC	abr-24	LINKEDIN	3562	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7186628710622498816/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	PAPER CSIC
POST	HYSYTECH	WEBINAR ABOUT CONVERSION TECHNOLOGIES	mar-24	LINKEDIN	3562	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171831475086999553/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	WEBINAR ABOUT CONVERSION TECHNOLOGIES
POST	HYSYTECH	WEBINAR RECORDING	abr-24	LINKEDIN	3562	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7194690855989850112/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	WEBINAR RECORDING
POST	HYSYTECH	GA PERSEO	may-24	LINKEDIN	3618	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7199756612633247745/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	GA PERSEO
POST	HYSYTECH	WEBINAR RECORDING	may-24	LINKEDIN	3618	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206991105853165569/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	WEBINAR RECORDING
REPOST	HYSYTECH	REVIEW MEETING SOON	jun-24	LINKEDIN	3675	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7206991105853165569/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	REVIEW MEETING SOON
REPOST	HYSYTECH	CATCO2NVERS SDGs	jun-24	LINKEDIN	3675	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206991760659537922/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	CATCO2NVERS SDGs
REPOST	HYSYTECH	MEETECH SPAIN 2024	jun-24	LINKEDIN	3675	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7212047682175983616/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	MEETECH2024 SPAIN

REPOST	HYSYTECH	VIDEO TECHNOLOGIES CARTIF	jun-24	LINKEDIN	3675	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7212048252882284545/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	VIDEO TECHNOLOGIES CARTIF
REPOST	HYSYTECH	NEWSLETTER 7	24-sep	LINKEDIN	3800	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7242896969155723266/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	NEWSLETTER 7
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL PROJECT VIDEO	24-sep	LINKEDIN	3800	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7239215208089452544/?actorCompanyId=76843420	YES	YES	FINAL PROJECT VIDEO
REPOST	HYSYTECH	INNO NEWS PRESS IMPACT	24-ago	LINKEDIN	3800	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7236365375880232960/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	INNO NEWS PRESS IMPACT
REPOST	HYSYTECH	TRAILER FINAL VIDEO	24-ago	LINKEDIN	3800	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7223990448732725248/?actorCompanyId=76843420	YES	YES	TRAILER FINAL VIDEO
REPOST	HYSYTECH	PAPER CSIC	24-oct	LINKEDIN	3800	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7251999866111856640/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	NO	CSIC PAPER
REPOST	HYSYTECH	ZENODO	oct-24	LINKEDIN	3800	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7252001230477029376/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	NO	ZENODO
REPOST	HYSYTECH	ELEARNING MATERIALS	24-nov	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264595417277849601/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	ELEARNING MATERIALS
REPOST	HYSYTECH	WHITEPAPER CARBON CAPTURE	nov-24	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7264598134914252800/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	WHITEPAPER CARBON CAPTURE
REPOST	HYSYTECH	CO2NVERSION TECHNOLOGIES	nov-24	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7264599715525107712/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	CO2NVERSION TECHNOLOGIES
POST	HYSYTECH	CATCO2NVERSIONS AND MERLIN PROJECT	dic-24	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7269761197535580160/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	CATCO2NVERSIONS AND MERLIN PROJECT
REPOST	HYSYTECH	CATCO2NVERSIONS GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN TURIN	dic-24	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7270451756860329984/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	CATCO2NVERSIONS GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN TURIN
REPOST	HYSYTECH	EU REDUCES CO2 EMISSIONS	dic-24	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7270455243551764480/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	EU REDUCES CO2 EMISSIONS
REPOST	HYSYTECH	Scientific Paper	ene-25	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7283146336806277120/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	Scientific Paper
REPOST	HYSYTECH	conversion technologies website section	ene-25	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7286006510923517953/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	conversion technologies website section
REPOST	HYSYTECH	Press release impacts	ene-25	LINKEDIN	4000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7286008472482045952/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	Press release impacts
REPOST	HYSYTECH	Paper CSIC	mar-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7300806731339628545/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	PAPER CSIC
REPOST	HYSYTECH	NEWSLETTER 8	mar-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7305262730867798016/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	NEWSLETTER 8
REPOST	HYSYTECH	NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION	mar-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7310269608173694976/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL EVENT CO2SMOS	abr-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7313476289149976592/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT CO2SMOS
REPOST	HYSYTECH	SCIENTIFIC PAPERS SECTION	abr-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7316457609077710848/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	SCIENTIFIC PAPERS SECTION
REPOST	HYSYTECH	NEWSLETTER 8	abr-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7320391748944318465/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	NEWSLETTER 8

POST	HYSYTECH	MILESTONE PROTOTYPE	abr-25	LINKEDIN	4200	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7318981092487716864/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	MILESTONE PROTOTYPE
WEBSITE POST	HYSYTECH	MILESTONE PROTOTYPE	abr-25	HYSYTECH WEBSITE	NA	https://www.hysytech.com/News/catco2nvers-prototype-installation-eng	NO	YES	MILESTONE PROTOTYPE
POST	HYSYTECH	Next Month M48 GA	may-25	Linekdln	4300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7331307249694412803/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	Next Month M48 GA
POST	HYSYTECH	New Partners Leda and Novamont	may-25	Linekdln	4300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7328730400615239681/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	New partners
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL EVENT CATCO2NVERS	jul-25	LINKEDIN	4300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7351599784916393986/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT CATCO2NVERS
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL EVENT PRESS RELEASE	sep-25	LINKEDIN	4300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:73771847611651297281/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT PRESS RELEASE
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL EVENT PRESS RELEASE	sep-25	LINKEDIN	4600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7371849594395148290/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT PRESS RELEASE
REPOST	HYSYTECH	ZENODO COMMUNITY	OCTOBER 2025	LINKEDIN	4600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7382407301925871616/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	Zenodo Community
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL EVENT	OCTOBER 2025	LINKEDIN	4600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7377306441835155456/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT
REPOST	HYSYTECH	FINAL EVENT PROMO	SEPTEMBER 2025	LINKEDIN	4600	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7377306441835155456/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT PROMO
PERSEO									
POST	PERSEO	FINAL EVENT	OCTOBER 2025	LINKEDIN	2300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7381298077804077059/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT
DANNA									
REPOST	DANNA	FINAL PROJECT VIDEO	24-sep	TWITTER	3200	https://x.com/Catco2N/status/1833408819130450271	NO	YES	FINAL PROJECT VIDEO
NOVAMONT									
REPOST	NOVAMONT	FINAL EVENT CATCO2NVERS	jul-25	LINKEDIN	4300	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7356248269900906496/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT CATCO2NVERS
SIE									
POST	SIE	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN	nov-24	LINKEDIN	8900	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7265319083691167744/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN
POST	SIE	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN	nov-24	TWITTER	1270	https://x.com/SustainableInnE/status/1859556942626054290	NO	YES	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN
POST	SIE	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN	nov-24	INSTAGRAM	590	https://www.instagram.com/p/DCoazhXor88/?img_index=1	NO	YES	GENERAL ASSEMBLY TURIN
POST	SIE	CSIC TESTIMONIAL	ene-25	LINKEDIN	9000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7284855870121791488/?commentUrn=urn%3A%3Acomment%3A%28activity%3A7284855870121791488%2C7284860613984473089%29&dashCommentUrn=urn%3A%3Acomment%3A%28activity%3A7284855870121791488%2C7284860613984473089%29&actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	TESTIMONIAL CSIC
POST	SIE	CSIC TESTIMONIAL	ene-25	TWITTER	1200	https://x.com/SustainableInnE/status/1879093042902380841	NO	YES	TESTIMONIAL CSIC
POST	SIE	CSIC TESTIMONIAL	ene-25	INSTAGRAM	576	https://www.instagram.com/p/DEzOQwoslMG/	NO	YES	TESTIMONIAL CSIC
POST	SIE	GA M48	may-25	LINKEDIN	9187	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7333141192232030208/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	GA M48
POST	SIE	GA M48	may-25	TWITTER	1259	https://x.com/SustainableInnE/status/1927373225526198720	NO	YES	GA M48

POST	SIE	GA M48	may-25	INSTAGRAM	576	https://www.instagram.com/p/DKKT8I0sDqs/?img_index=1	NO	YES	GA M48
POST	SIE	FINAL EVENT PROMO	sep-25	LINKEDIN	9000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7368562053365530627/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	PROMO FINAL EVENT
POST	SIE	FINAL EVENT PROMO	sep-25	TWITTER	1000	https://x.com/SustainableInnE/status/1962799084135141443	NO	YES	PROMO FINAL EVENT
POST	SIE	FINAL EVENT	OCTOBER 2025	LINKEDIN	9000	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7379156021451055104/?actorCompanyId=76843420	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT
POST	SIE	FINAL EVENT	OCTOBER 2025	TWITTER	1000	https://x.com/SustainableInnE/status/1973390522099048685	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT
POST	SIE	FINAL EVENT	OCTOBER 2025	INSTAGRAM	500	https://www.instagram.com/p/DPRRk2KDjQM/?img_index=1	NO	YES	FINAL EVENT
EVENT	SIE	FINAL EVENT	OCTOBER 2025	MADRID	40	https://catco2nvers.eu/2025/10/13/final-project-event/	YES	YES	FINAL EVENT IN CSIC